

Support Supervision Analysis and Implementation of Quality of Primary Education in Uganda

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ABSTRACT

According to this study, effective support supervision is crucial for the improvement of quality primary schooling in Uganda. Quantitative and qualitative methods were used to assess primary and secondary data and analyse support supervision as an effective activity focused on improvement in the quality of education. A minimum mean value of 1 and a maximum average value of 4 were used to help interpret the data from the respondents and other relevant information obtained from the documents reviewed. School supervision practices in primary schools was regarded extremely effective at the mean ranging from 3.26 to 4.00. Additionally, the results shown in Table 4.5 from the respondents generally regarded support supervision in primary schools as effective at the average mean value of 2.59, which corresponds to effectiveness in the rating scale at a comparatively low standard deviation of 0.81.

According to 'How we inspect' document (MoES, 2012) support supervision is a critical aspect of management that involves overseeing the work of teachers and providing mentorship support to ensure that they perform their tasks effectively. However, issues of ineffectiveness in support supervision such as lack of support, inadequate feedback during and after supervision of teaching hinder their ability to perform effectively. Teachers may feel uncertain of what is expected of them and may not improve their performance if effective support is not given. Therefore the stakeholders who are directly responsible for effective support supervision should collectively strive to provide clear guidance and feedback on teaching performance when supervision is done. It is essential that clear guidelines for performance are established to help teachers be aware of the criteria they are evaluated on. This will help the teachers to understand what they need to do to improve and be able to focus their efforts towards improvement of quality education.

DECLARATION OF AUTHORSHIP

I, Kazooba Atuhairwe Caroline, hereby declare that this dissertation is entirely original and has not been submitted to any university or college for consideration for any other academic honour and any assistance that was received in the preparation of this study is fully acknowledged and disclosed in the paper. I also certify that this paper was prepared by me specifically for the partial fulfillment for the degree of Master of Research and Public Policy at Uganda Christian University.

Signature----- Date: 13/5/2023

Kazooba Atuhairwe Caroline

APPROVAL

With my consent as the University's Research Supervisor, this dissertation has been turned in for defence.

Signature----- Date: 13/5/2023

Alfred Wamurubu (PhD)

DEDICATION

This dissertation is dedicated to God, my devoted husband, Mr. Samuel Kazooba, my mother Mrs. Jane Rubahika, and the young people of Uganda, including my children -- Joe, Esther, Immanuel, Joseph, and Ephraim -- who go on to profit from universal education.

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GLOSSARY OF TERMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

ADEA	:	Association for the Development of Education in Africa
BA ED	:	Bachelor of Arts Education
BED	:	Bachelor of Education
BED	:	Basic Education Department
BoG	:	Board of Governors
BRMS	:	Basic Requirements and Minimum Standards
BTVET	:	Business, Technical, Vocational Education and Training
COVID-19	:	Corona Virus Disease 2019
C-PEL	:	Certificate of Proficiency in Education Leadership
C-PT	:	Certificate of Proficiency in Teaching
C-TEP	:	Certificate in Teacher Education Proficiency
DEO	:	District Education Officer
DES	:	Directorate of Education Standards
EFA	:	Education for All
ESA	:	Education Standards Agency
ESC	:	Education Service Commission
ESD	:	Education for Sustainable Development
ESIP	:	Education Sector Investment Plan
ESSP	:	Education Sector Strategic Plan
FAWEU:		Forum for African Women Educationists in Uganda
GEPs	:	Global Education Policies
IICBA	:	International Institute for Capacity Building in Africa
IIEP	:	International Institute for Education Planning
KCCA	:	Kampala Capital City Authority
KYU	:	Kyambogo University
LABE	:	Literacy and Adult Basic Education
MA ED	:	Master of Arts in Education
MDG	:	Millennium Development Goal
MED	:	Master of Education
MoES	:	Ministry of Education and Sports
NCDC	:	National Curriculum Development Centre
OECD	:	Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
OAG	:	Office of the Auditor General
PDE	:	Procuring and Disposing Entity
PDEs	:	Procurement and Disposal Entities
PPDA	:	Public Procurement and Disposal of Assets
QEI	:	Quality Enhancement Initiative
QIs	:	Quality Indicators
QUED	:	Quality Educator
SDG	:	Sustainable Development Goal
SIP	:	School Improvement Plan
SMC	:	School Management Committee
SPRs	:	School Performance Reviews
SWAp	:	Sector Wide Approach
TETD	:	Teacher Education Training and Development
TIET	:	Teacher Instructor Education and Training Department of MOES
TISSA	:	Teacher Initiative in Sub-Saharan Africa
UIS	:	UNESCO Institute for Statistics
UNATCOM	:	Uganda National Commission for UNESCO
UNATU:		Uganda National Teachers Union
UNESCO	:	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNICEF	:	United Nations Children's Fund
UPE	:	Universal Primary Education
UPE	:	Universal Primary Education
WHO	:	World Health Organization

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

A. Introduction

Fruitful execution of Universal Primary Education (UPE) requires the association of a multitude of partners who guarantee viable instruction administration conveyance. The Ministry of Education and Sports (MoES), along with Kyambogo University (KYU) and the Directorate of Education Standards Agency (ESA) as the partners inside the Education area, planned the essential educator capability profile as an expert instrument for quality improvement in 2004. The plan distinguished the instructor support point as one of the means for further developed training administration conveyance. Quality improvement is a significant part of any help conveyance framework. In the school system in Uganda, is the ESA as the quality affirmation arm of the Ministry of Education and Sports (MoES) that was subsequently changed into the Directorate of Education Standards (DES) following the sanctioning of the Education Act of 2008 to complete improvement exercises. And support supervision is one of the priority areas for improvement (MoES, 2012).

The motivation behind this review zeroed in on the instructor-related issues that influence the quality training in Public elementary schools. Among the issues that impacted essential schooling was instructor truancy. In this way, to encourage the execution of value in Primary Education in UPE schools, the MoES along with different partners ensured that help oversight was done as one of the improvement exercises to guarantee quality confirmation of management and screen the advancement of school execution surveys (SPRs). Different partners incorporate the Senior Education officials and collaborator training officials that are straightforwardly liable for reinforcing proficient reflective competence by administering educators to show that they care about what occurs in the study hall and rousing instructors to be available in school (UPE, 2004).

Reflective competence is an expert advancement technique which establishes in the constructivist worldview, the conversations of the vital convictions about information and learning with going with instructive rules. Constructivism obviously centres around the significant job that the instructor plays in supporting the growing experience as a talented facilitator (Osterman, 1998, 2014). In Uganda's Education setting, Reflective practice is fortified through School Performance Reviews and backing oversight during school examination. This is on the grounds that essential instructors are critical to advancing manageable advancement targets, and are liable for quality result in educating and learning. The Universal Primary Education strategy (UPE) puts accentuation on the estimation and assessment of value measures and norms in its execution to accomplish Universal quality schooling.

In any case, all partners from the different Education offices like District Education Department, DES, Basic Education Guidelines, Directorate of Education in KCCA and Teacher Education Development and Training (TEDT) are ready to set up a quality affirmation instrument in the light of composed report after investigation/oversight of the essential educators to illuminate their dynamic cycle. The holes in the oversight of instructors have made space for phantom students, educators and even apparition schools or potentially non-appearance of the two, instructors and students (ESSP FY 2017/18 - 2019/20), and hence influencing the nature of Universal essential training. Quality upgrades in essential training are conceivable when support management of educators is cautiously and really carried out. The educators will require close oversight mentorship for quality proportions of their expert appearance in instructing for quality information sources and enhancements in the students' learning results.

Educators are extremely strong specialists of value Education. Schooling in Uganda is a groundbreaking apparatus and UPE is one of the instructive projects that have been executed beginning around 2004 to take care of any potential issues in training. For the most part, schooling adds to maintainable financial and social development through all inclusive proficiency rates coming about because of huge speculation. UPE as a venture assembles the useful limit of the individuals from its general public where the nature of its instructors stays key in adding to expanded abundance by making solid and security mindfulness among the populace and engaging people to think freely to lead sound and secure lives (MoES, 2010).

The public authority White Paper on Education (1992) bases on the philosophy that "No nation can show improvement over the nature of its school system." Mwalimu Julius Nyerere was likewise cited in it saying, "No schooling system can be preferable over the nature of its instructors." The public authority White Paper on Education (1992) has been key in the advancement of educator strategy changes. The Bible mentions in Luke 40:6 that, "an understudy is on par with his educator." If the instructors fizzle at instructing, the understudies will likewise come up short at learning. This review targets evaluating the impact that this help oversight on quality Education gave in elementary schools in Kampala Capital City Authority.

The study's backdrop, problem statement, objectives, questions for investigation, hypothesis of research, conceptual structure, study scope, study significance, research rationale, and operational descriptions of phrases and ideas are all presented in this chapter.

B. Background to the Study

In the present worldwide world, educators who are not upheld to develop and create in their calling cannot ensure nature of instruction.

Internationally, the worldwide training plans or Education changes have been underlined in the Sustainable Development objectives and Universal interest in schooling for all. What is more, this has given countries in the land masses of Asia and so on admittance to accomplish feasible monetary development. The nature of instruction is one of the key need areas that should be acknowledged in the creation of nations and for their schooling system to deliver comparative training and advancements of SDGs 4 and 4.7 for quality instruction and worldwide skill separately. Universally, the educators are crucial and are a way to understanding the worldwide focuses of value schooling and acknowledge worldwide skills in their instructing calling. Worldwide capability is complex and incorporates mental turn of events, socio-enthusiastic abilities and municipal acquiring (OECD/Asia Society, 2018).

Likewise, across Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), the Education sectors set forth energy to adjust the SDG 4 to the Education for All (EFA) Goal 6 to accomplish quality Education where SDG 4.c is a method for strategy execution to accomplish all the SDG 4 targets. Globally, the educators are a crucial condition to ensuring nature of essential training. Notwithstanding, there are a few key difficulties that hamper the arrangement of value training which incorporate the nature of instructing, both concerning data sources and learning results (13.4 per cent in 2010/11). Likewise, the teachers in Africa are unconnected from constructive involvement in the discourse around educational improvement and yet their inputs in self-evaluation, documentation and sharing experiences are important for quality improvements. The lack of support supervision has affected teaching performance which is so significant in adding to the learning results if performance indicators and quality indicators are provided with clear guidelines and instructions for improving the quality of education. The lack of support such as guidance on teacher strengthening and viable school authority give a stage to them to partake in the discourse around instructive improvement has not been effectively provided. If there is no stage for the educators' voices in approach for quality enhancements in schooling, it becomes difficult to accomplish SDG 4.7 of value instruction and the objectives of the Continental Education Strategy for Africa. The Education for All (EFA) Global Monitoring Report (2011), the UNESCO Institute of Statistics (2012) demonstrate that nations in Sub-Saharan Africa face training difficulties that incorporate the nature of instructing, both as far as sources of information and learning results that require observing of instructor weakening on a yearly premise, for each level and subject specialization. Additionally, lack of thoroughly prepared instructors across Sub-Saharan Africa keeps on imperiling Quality Education (UNESCO, 2018).

Moreover, Maclure presents that West and Central African Teachers neither have the skill nor the base information regarding the matter and cannot educate actually on the grounds that they are not well ready for their work. For instance, inadequate feedback to teachers during and after supervision has resulted in poor performance. Their readiness is lacking or unimportant, or at times both (Maclure, 1997, 58-60). The teachers were seen ordinarily rehearsing content reflection because of the idea of the appraisal devices benefited them to assess their substance toward the finish of their illustrations. Content reflection by instructors essentially draws on what they by and by know or currently show which does not uphold the advancement of inventive and decisive reasoning abilities.

In present-day Uganda, one of the approaches to accomplishing feasible human asset advancement is through Universal Primary Education and will undoubtedly give positive effect on the existence of individuals and the national economy if effectively executed. Hence, to overcome issues of supervision, adequate support must be provided to the teachers in order to perform their duties effectively.

To help proficient practical competence among the instructors, the School Performance Reviews were instituted to fortify reflective performance and train instructors in Certificate in Teacher Education Proficiency (C-TEP). The Education and Sports Sector Strategic Plan (ESSP) 2017-2020 gave the approach structure that directs the Sector to explore through its aggressive objectives of giving quality instruction. The ESSP (2007) was then refreshed, re-projected and this provoked the expansion of six targets that zeroed in on expanding the attractiveness of the teaching profession through the presentation of a scheme of service to ensure that teachers and school overseers are strengthened and professionalized in order to contribute meaningfully to the achievement of quality education. The area's essential 6th goal was to extend access at all levels of the framework; increment value; guarantee importance; and work on the nature of the substance of instruction and its conveyance.

The ESSP (2010-2015) as a significant procedure was taken on to focus on access, value, pertinence and productivity of schooling administration conveyance through working on the adequacy and proficiency of the conveyance of training administrations at all levels by expanding the ability to design, oversee and screen for a superior presentation (MoES, 2010d).

The policymakers, for example, the Ministers and government authorities in reference to the Government White paper on Education (1992) and different partners with the Ministry of Education and Sports, have since been occupied with the purpose to provide technical support, guide, coordinate, regulate and promote quality education.

For example, Ministry of Education and sports with the quality of Educators (QUED) projects' which was spearheaded by FAWEU and LABE, ESA/DES and UNATU and among other stakeholders developed Primary Teacher Competence Profile liable for fortifying the essential teacher skills that impact the nature of essential schooling.

Be that as it may, execution of value Education has been hampered by muddled agreement between Kyambogo University (2004) and Directorate of Education standards (2005) who work under the Ministry of Education and sports perceived themselves as separate elements when it originated to the supervision for the use of Teacher Competence Profile by the teachers. Their two profiles were not harmonized due to muddled agreement and yet they entail similar quality teacher indicators measured for quality teaching performance. Along these lines, this perplexed agreement on who is answerable for reinforcing essential teachers' competences has impacted the nature of schooling since there is no collaboration in such a manner.

While the essential instructor skill profiles were spread to the significant partners from the various locales of Pader, Lamwo, Dokolo, Otuke, Lira, Nakaseke, Gomba, Kyegegwa, Kyenjojo, Luwero, Gulu and Mpigi, it was accounted for that the profiles were not being utilized. Thus there are gaps in coordinating profiles and a lack of mindfulness (MoES, 2010) regarding how the device should be used during assessments. Additionally, there is a need for guidelines on how educators can effectively utilize technology to enhance the quality of primary education. Educators' expert intelligent abilities are basic for accomplishing quality enhancements in the students' results.

It is not shocking that instructors are still observed not to be totally ready to educate in multi-grade circumstances or encourage the abilities of working with kids with assorted learning capacities and styles in a similar homeroom (Little, 2006).

Notwithstanding the abovementioned, when Uganda took part in the Southern and Eastern Africa Consortium for Monitoring Educational Quality (SACMEQ) evaluation in 2007 at a worldwide level, focusing on 235 government schools across the country (SACMEQ, 2010a), it was affirmed that the degree of instruction quality was low as the consequence of the common forcibly feeding sort of showing technique utilized by educators and insufficient utilization of course readings and illustrative materials in study hall examples (IOB, 2008); the numerous younger grade students whose learning and accomplishments are to a great extent hampered by shortcomings in instructors' academic abilities and homeroom rehearses (Mulindwa & Marshall, 2013). And these are issues of that arise as a result of inadequate support supervision.

Notwithstanding, the nature of instruction is not just impacted by instructors' non-attendance nor their shortcomings in academic abilities and study hall rehearses, yet in addition a decrease in help management of educators in schools in country regions because of unfortunate reviews. In any event, when it is done confirmed information gathered and criticism on instructors' appearance on their educating are seldom given when insight measures and principles are finished during homeroom oversight. Thus, during the oversight of essential instructors, the interaction and reason reflection actually must happen through instrumental, open, and liberator types of learning and these educational experiences address signs of reflection (Kreber, 2004). Thus, it is in this cycle that the educators need adequate mentorship to reflect actually and fundamentally for enhancements in the students' learning accomplishments. Confirmed information on intelligent results of educators turns out to be extremely helpful in tending to areas of expert reflection that might require fortifying in the cycles of checking, assessment and guaranteeing compelling execution of all instructor-related polices in TIET and programmes and for quality assistance conveyance in the Education Sector.

For the most part, there is an extraordinary clamour for the Ministry of Education and Sports to fortify the holes in help oversight in accordance with the execution head of School Performance Reviews that actions the viability of instructing. Notwithstanding, confirmed information on instructor quality markers when decided by insight appear to be deficient in the reports that would be applicable to giving earnest illuminating to direct arrangement choices on affecting intelligent educating in the homeroom to accomplish quality essential training.

C. Statement of the Problem

Globally, education goals for sustainable human resource development depend on the teacher pillar that is supported by education stakeholders to guarantee the quality of education for all. These goals for Quality and Inclusive Education have since been severely hampered by the lack of professional development where teacher quality has been compromised notably obvious in nations wherein the system of education has been successful in increasing student enrolment and hiring of teachers in developing countries (Quality Educators for All, 2012).

The Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4.7 target 4.c, and Education for All (EFA) Goal 6 that aim at achieving quality Education continue to be affected by the quality of teaching (UNESCO, 2018 and Basic Education Sector Analysis Report, 2012)

The provision of high-quality education in Uganda is hampered by several major issues, including the calibre of teaching in both terms of inputs and learning outcomes at 13.4 per cent in 2010/11 (UNESCO, 2018) which are due to issues that arise from inspection.

The issues of effectiveness in support supervision of teachers as an aspect for quality improvement have led to inadequate feedback. Supervisors have not been able to accumulate statistical evidence to inform decisions to guide further progress in teacher performance. It is clear that the lack of effective support to teachers during supervision of teachers has also contributed to the low level of education quality which is seen in the prevalent force-feeding type of teaching method employed by teachers (SACMEQ, 2010; IOB, 2008). This has made it difficult to provide pupils with a high-quality education, as evidenced by teachers' pedagogical skill deficiencies and poor classroom management (Mulindwa & Marshall, 2013). More importantly, it has given room for ghost teachers, ghost students, and teacher absenteeism (ESSP FY 2017/18 – 2019/20).

This study analysed support supervision as an improvement activity which ensures quality primary education.

D. Purpose and Objectives

The purpose of this study was to analyse support supervision as an effective activity focused on quality improvements in primary school education.

➤ *Specific Objectives*

- To analyse support supervision as an effective activity towards the improvement of quality of primary school education in Uganda;
- To analyse the stakeholders' role and responsibilities in the Ministry of Education and Sports towards the improvement quality primary education in Uganda;
- To establish if mentorship support for professional practice leads to the improvement in quality primary education in Uganda;
- To examine the significance of School Performance Reviews on the improvement of quality primary education in Uganda.

E. Research Questions

- How effective is support supervision towards the improvement of quality primary education in Uganda?
- What are the roles and responsibilities of the Stakeholders that foster the improvement of quality primary education in Uganda?
- Does mentorship support for professional practice lead to the improvement in the quality primary education in Uganda?
- What is the significance of School Performance Reviews on the improvement of quality primary education in Uganda?

F. Research Hypotheses

- Quality of primary school education is dependent on effective support supervision as an element of School inspections.
- Quality of primary school education is dependent on the Stakeholders' responsibilities in the Ministry of Education and Sports.
- Quality of primary school education is dependent on Mentorship support for professional practice.
- Quality of primary school education is dependent on School Performance Reviews.

G. Scope of the Study

The scope of the study comprised geographical scope, content scope and time scope as presented below.

➤ *Geographical Scope*

The study was conducted in Kampala Capital City of Uganda. This was favoured on the grounds that the MoES goes about as an organizing place for the Sector Wide Approach (SWAP) for executing the Monitoring and Evaluation of System in surveying instructive requirements of all leaders, spreading data through complete announcing components and guaranteeing that necessities are met in an effective and convenient way. Observing and Evaluation structures measure progress in accomplishing need vital area goals of access, value, quality and productivity (ESSP FY 2017/18 - 2019/20).

MoES and their counterparts from Kampala piloted the Certificate of Proficiency in Teaching (C-PTFifteen (15) districts in North-eastern Uganda (MoES, 2010) to improve quality education. Therefore, this geographical scope was considered because the resourceful information that was needed for this study could be got from Education Officers and Administrators from the local governments at the District, Directorate Education KCCA and Education Standards, Basic Education Department (BED) and School administrators who share responsibilities to foster the improvement of UPE for quality improvements. It was therefore befitting to locate the study on Support Supervision provided by the various stakeholders under the MoES in providing quality education.

➤ *Content Scope*

The study focused on the evaluation on help management execution for nature of grade school instruction. The review assessed gaps in support management and examined the role of mentorship in strengthening career reflection. It also provided recommendations to policy-makers regarding the effectiveness of this approach in enhancing the quality of education by improving educators' performance and achievement."

➤ *The Time Scope*

Because the ESA through the Ministry of Education and Sports was established into legislation to provide an impartial and outside assessment of educational quality, the study took data spanning a period of 10 (ten) years from 2000 to 2010 into consideration. Additionally, the time frame includes the second stage of implementing the UPE policy. The Education Standards Agency (ESA) was renamed the Directorate of Education Standards (DES) after the Education Act of 2008 was passed, and it was given the guidelines and the duty to carry out self-evaluations and evaluations over school performance reviews in order to achieve quality education.

H. *Justification of the Study*

- First and foremost, the research clearly brings out the research evidence on support supervision towards the improvement of the quality of primary school education.
- The research results of this study offer information on the stakeholders' shared responsibilities for improving the standard of primary school education in Uganda and how these results can be translated into an implementation strategy that creates an environment that is conducive to successful support supervision interventions.
- The research's findings shed light on the question of whether supporting teachers through mentorship is the best way to deepen their professional reflection and help them realize their teaching competences for quality improvement in primary school education. If it was determined that the same would have a significant impact on raising the standard of elementary education, recommendations would be made.
- Besides, this research provides literature on the existing information on the significance of the School Performance Review reports and highlights the gaps that would need the attention of policy implementers so as to come up with appropriate intervention measures on the evaluation of specific teachers' standards of profession reflection.

I. *Significance of the Study*

The information that has been established regarding support supervision will be used as a foundation for raising the standard of instruction in primary schools.

The results will be integrated into an existing body of knowledge to raise the standard of primary school instruction.

J. *Theoretical Framework*

This study was guided by the Institutional Theory and the Constructivist Thinking Theory as explained in the details below.

➤ *Institutional Theory*

Public theory alludes to how government expects to accomplish specific objectives. For example, UPE is a strategy that was set up to guarantee that all Ugandan youngsters from seven years or more go to class and finish their schooling in order to carry on with better lives. Also, this could be conceivable by the educators' association who are the motivation behind why children go to classes. Institutional hypothesis or institutionalism connotes the job of organizations which obliges and enables the human way of behaving. There is no single approach to characterizing organizations and different institutional methodologies characterize foundations in their particular manner (Knill & Tosun, 2012, p.76). Be that as it may, the institutional methodology depicts the more formal and legitimate parts of government organizations and their proper design, lawful powers, procedural guidelines, and capacities. Institutional designs, plans, and methodology frequently have significant ramifications for the reception and content of public arrangements that give part of the setting to strategy making, which are considered alongside the more unique parts of legislative issues, like ideological groups, gatherings, and general assessment in affecting the approach cycle. With regard to this review, institutional hypothesis gives clarifications of how the various partners from the various establishments are seen while coordinating their endeavours properly as they continued looking for instructor improvement. These remember different players for the essential schooling sub-area ordered by the Ministry of Education and Sports to bring out various jobs through the various educator strategy changes in TIET that further develop instructor quality while drawing on the public arrangement examination process including the entertainers, or various individuals from various foundations, for example, Teacher Instructor Education and Training (TIET), Forum for African Women Educationalists Uganda Chapter (FAWEU), MoES, Kyambogo University (KYU), Literacy and Adult Basic Education (LABE), National Curriculum Development Centre (NCDC), Uganda National Teachers' Union (UNATU), Directorate of Education Standards(DES), UNITY Project, and UNATCOM and so forth with an intent to support the educator point of support among different points of support for worked on quality training.

➤ *Constructivist Thinking Theory*

Strategy changes in TIET currently called Teacher Education Training and Development (TETD) foundations are planned to work on nature of Education administration. School Performance Reviews fortify the intelligent act of educators to accomplish quality students' learning results. Among the approach changes, the Certificate in Teacher Education Proficiency (C-TEP) was created. C-TEP is the Certificate in Teacher Education Proficiency course founded on the constructivist thinking hypothesis where the student is shown how to learn while the educator turns into a gifted facilitator or an intelligent master. C-TEP programme underscores intelligent practice to empower educator experts to look at their degree of execution and make a move to a more elevated level. Bringing up the significance of appearance in instructors' expert way of behaving and its pertinence in their expert turn of events, different creators -- for instance, Killeavy and Moloney (2010) -- featured the capacity to consider practice as the

reason for learning; and individual encounters are significant in the educators' advancement today, and reflection is one technique that supports such turn of events (Shoffner, 2009); the capacity to reflect develops out of our encounters both as an expert and an individual (Scanlan & Chernomas, 1997).

In the light of Constructivism thinking hypothesis, an intelligent professional is one who has finely levelled up observational abilities and has clear and cautious portrayal of experience(observation) which turns into the reason for the later periods of the intelligent practice cycle; evaluation, re-conceptualization and trial and error. Constructivism obviously centres around the significant pretended by the instructor in supporting the educational experience however characterizes this job basically as a facilitator who guides development by centring request, connecting with understudies, investigating and testing thoughts, giving assets, surveying understudies' advancement, and giving valuable criticism.

Finally, Constructivism recognizes a significant wellspring of disequilibrium as the differentiation between private activity speculations and those hypotheses from the conventional information base. Under the information base, the educator advances by laying out request boundaries. Here in an expert advancement homeroom, the instructors recognize themes or errands and give assets to direct the students' request and these requirements are consistent with constructivist principles that support quality in education. This proper information could likewise be utilized as a way to challenge the understudy's earlier suppositions. In these examples, formal hypothesis was an asset and a device for learning, not just as 'truth' to be conveyed and ingested.

K. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

According to Camp (2001), the researcher feels that this structure is best able to clarify the phenomenon under the study's natural course of development. It is related to the theories, notions, and empirical research that the researcher used to set up and support the data that she promoted (Peshkin, 1993).

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework

The purpose of Figure 1 above is to describe how Support supervision affects Quality Education. The three variables—Independent, Dependent, and Intervening—are represented by the framework. The elementary education quality is affected by the two variables (the independent variable and the intervening variable). To promote the quality of primary education, effective support supervision should result in improved adherence to policies and procedures as established in the Education Sector Strategic Plan 2017/18- 2019/20 and Universal Primary Education Policies, and how well we inspect part 3, and how well are our school-led documents designed to improve the quality of education.

Support supervision is an independent variable, meaning that it cannot be affected by other factors that are being measured. In an experiment, the dependent variable (quality of education) is one that has been tested or measured. Support supervision enhances the performance of individuals or teams, for instance the teachers. The statutory body DES, under MoES, provides basic guidelines to ensure the effectiveness of support supervision as the intervening variable. The principles used for the research were described in order to comprehend the natural course of the occurrence being studied as follows, in order to comprehend it and clarify what supports great education.

➤ *Support Supervision*

In Uganda, the Education Standards Agency (ESA) currently known as the Directorate of Education Standards (DES) started its activities in July 2001 and with the Key parts of the assessment approach that incorporated a fore-ordained construction of Quality Indicators (QIs, for example, i) the attention on proof, ii) an accentuation on revealing the two qualities and shortcomings, and iii) empowering self-assessment with respect to the establishment and its head instructor or head.

Management and Inspection are terms that are frequently utilized reciprocally. Support management is characterized as a course of assisting the educating with staffing to consistently further develop their own work execution. It is done in a deferential and non-dictatorial way with an attention on involving administrative visits as a chance to further develop information and abilities of the class instructors (WHO, 2008).

Effective support Supervision in UPE schools is done as an approach to showing the instructors that the managers care about what educators instruct in the study hall and enhance job satisfaction.

Support supervision is one of the activities under school inspection that includes classroom observation, checking lesson plans which is done by the senior education officer and senior staff. Support supervision contributes to improvement in part 2: How well is our school led? (MoES, 2012).

In support supervision, head teachers, deputy head teachers, senior education assistants, senior staff and CCTs use BRMS and the rest of this guide on evaluating and improving the quality of education to help both the supervisor and the teachers plan for improvement according to Part 2: How well is our school led? (MoES, 2012).

The School Inspection system as the overall gives a guide on what to assess in each investigation and of each phase of review during arranging, during the genuine examination visits and composing of the Inspection reports. The key spotlight is on the idea of youngsters' learning, care and backing needs and the degree to which the school is effective in addressing these necessities.

Assessment is generally arranged by a set pattern of exercises to work on the nature of instruction in UPE schools. The evaluators who are outside the school are directed on unambiguous quality markers that are to be assessed, estimated and detailed. The emphasis is likewise on the educators' preparation, instructing and growing experience, evaluation, recording and announcing of the instructors' information, among others. Investigation is otherwise called outer assessment that happens at public level though crafted by auditors in the Directorate of Education Standards.

➤ *Stakeholders' Responsibilities*

The MoES, along with any remaining partners in essential instruction, work inseparably to distinguish the ideal abilities of the grade teacher in Uganda. In any case, the obligation of oversight of instructor profile is as yet compromised. Supervisors are expected to have increased knowledge and skills in order to provide effective support supervision before and after the support supervision activities.

As part of their responsibilities, they need to improve job satisfaction among supervised individuals in primary schools through feedback mechanisms, such as teacher conferencing, and provide documented assessments of competence profiles. These assessments will inform future actions to take and reviews.

So, for effective support supervision, the Ministry of Education and Sports under the Quality Educators' (QUED) Project with a group of specialists were to: i) concentrate on the general points and goals of essential instruction in Uganda; ii) review and make discussions about the current essential instructor capability profiles to figure out why they were not being used in Uganda; and iii) gather data from skill profiles for different nations which can be utilized during the time spent drafting the new essential instructor ability profile for Uganda; iv) assemble ideas from partners on the skills they expect of a successful grade teacher; v) then, at that point, accumulate an easy-to-understand draft essential instructor capability profile that would be applicable to the ongoing training needs of Uganda. All endeavours were enormously impacted. The group of specialists accumulated data about the utilization of the current profiles from the areas of Lamwo, Pader, Dokolo, Lira, Otuke, Gomba, Nakaseke, Kyenjojo, Kyegegwa, Luwero, Mpigi and Gulu. What is more, it was not satisfactory on who was to circle back to the elementary teacher profile since a portion of the profiles had essentially been racked by educators and were not known by a larger number of people of different partners.

At the school board level, the senior instruction officials and their collaborators offer help to management by visiting the educators' study hall to show that they care about what takes place in the homeroom and as an approach to spurring them.

It is through the MoES that guidelines are authorized through administrative organizations like ESA/DES and different establishments like TIET and KYU. The Ministry brings the obligation to the table for proficient help and fosters training all through the country. In any case, absence of follow-up, the after-effect of the feebleness of bosses and of the intricacy of decision-production in an organization like the instructive organization, is disappointing to instructors and ruins the management framework.

Additionally, there are referenced holes in the arrangement of cooperative help oversight and the school overseers, and at neighbourhood level through crafted reviewers working inside regions, sub-areas and districts have prompted laxity in supporting the instructor point of support for worked-on quality and in this way there is high truancy among educators and understudies, educators' underperformance and henceforth terrible showing in schools (MoES, March 2010).

➤ *Mentorship*

Tutoring is an expert connection between a coach and a mentee with the end goal of expert guidance and direction. Kram, the most referred to creator on tutoring, contends that coaching is a kind of formative relationship wherein guides give two sorts of capacities: These skills include funding, willingness and permeability, instruction, assurance, and tasks for testing. On the other hand, psychosocial abilities are concerned with providing help and encouragement to the protégé. These abilities improve the likelihood that the protégé will be successful. Psychosocial capacities incorporate: acknowledgement, guiding, fellowship, and the job displaying. These capacities upgrade a singular's feeling of skill, character, and viability in an expert job (Kram, 1985:23).

Bowen (1985) and Mullen (2005) portrayed tutoring as one that happens when a senior individual (the guide with regard to progress in years and experience) gives data, exhortation and everyday encouragement to a lesser individual (i.e., the mentee) in a relationship enduring throughout a drawn out timeframe. Furthermore, such a relationship is known to be set apart by a significant enthusiastic responsibility by the two players.

Chosen Inspectors of School offer help mentorship on practical reflective competence to the school personnel to guarantee constant expert abilities, imaginative and decisive reasoning and problem solving abilities for worked on Quality sources of information and learning results. Joyce and Showers (1996) made sense of that companion instructing as a way to concentrate on teaching professional development while Cooper and Boyd (1996) depicted peer training as a methodology that refines educating rehearses. Thistle, McLeod and Goldsmith (2007) expressed that companion instructing supports intelligent practice. This is a region that commits sufficient consideration for distinguishing proof of mentorship regions for educators' expert competences that upgrade innovative and decisive reasoning for worked-on Quality data sources and scholarly results of the students. Along these lines, the authenticity of the chosen evaluators should be guaranteed to successfully utilize mentorship procedures during their oversight visits for further developed Quality assistance conveyance in grade schools.

➤ *School Performance Reviews*

The Inspectors in the DES Partners in Organizations assess within areas, sub-regions, and districts and follow an examination cycle to monitor the advancement of leading School Performance Reviews (SPR) overall: i) To strengthen reflective practice among staff, ii) To empower institutions ascertain challenges and lay proper techniques for overcoming these challenges, and iii) To upgrade School Enhancement Planning towards progress of Quality Education (MoES, 2010).

In 1993, Osterman and Kottkamp et al. saw one's ability to analyse experiences and actions as a singular endeavour and depicted as an aggregate cycle while featuring the significance of a gifted facilitator who is an instructor. Competence in expert practice, the instructor shares encounters typically drawn from their training and expertise.

Whenever the educator is defied with astonishing result(s), he is expected to venture back to inspect the experience, seeing goals, activities, and results. Through perception and examination, the issue will be all the more plainly characterized. Issue disparities among planned and real way of behaving or among objectives and genuine results go about as upgrade to learning. Accordingly, the capacity to recognize moves and lay fitting methodologies to defeat such difficulties makes the instructors innovative and basic scholars to tackle the issue of inconsistencies in their training for Quality Education.

Moreover, with regard to overseers' utilization of the apparatuses and techniques to gather proved information on quality instructing, decisions are made relying upon the steady use of these devices. Examiners cause decisions or assessments that appear to be more refined than information gathering. The methodology is supposed to be in danger of being overseen by non-experts to screen the training and arrangement in a singular school which stop a genuine shortcoming and a gamble to having emotional data on Quality Education. This is on the grounds that the instruments used to gather information measure least necessities in view of the Inspector's judgement whether the training or arrangement seen in schools fulfil the essential guideline or not and are normally met with a basic met/not met, yes/no, seen/not seen reaction set apart against an agenda.

With regard to gathering information, the seen/not seen approach has critical limitations when it is utilized as an investigation apparatus; for it does not resolve issues of value with regard to showing quality for worked-on Quality Education. For instance, the presence of illustration plans is less significant than whether example arranging is utilized successfully to further develop learning. Educators might create example plans; however, these might be of low quality or not really be applied while instructing, which is many times the situation. Instructors may now and then basically produce example intents to be seen by ranking directors or outer evaluators, and it very well may be too hard to separate between a viable and incapable educator. As a guideline, while searching for narrative proof among the instructors, the "What and how" educators really instruct is a higher priority than their message put down for auditors to check out. Information on Quality Education thinks more about the learning results as opposed to the quality contributions of the educators that add to Quality Education. Also, information is not completely accessible on Uganda's Education insights (Uganda Education Statistical Abstract, 2009).

➤ *Priority Interventions and Implementation of UPE Policy in the ESSP 2017-2020*

The Education and Sports Sector Strategic Plan (ESSP) 2017-2020 provided the policy framework that guides the Sector to navigate through its goals of providing quality education.

The Ministry of Education mediation intends to accomplish impartial admittance to pertinent and quality instruction and preparing of educators which depended on the 23 Presidential Rules 2016-2021, the NRM Election Manifesto, NDP II, International Policy Commitments and the Sector's SWOT Analysis. A powerful SWOT investigation of the Education and Sports Sector uncovered a solid political obligation to the Sector and the changed instruction strategy that introduced numerous non-state training suppliers as key qualities to go about as a springboard that will drive the area towards accomplishing its targets. Despite the qualities, there are shortcomings and dangers that posture difficulties to the accomplishment of its objectives like obsolete strategies and legitimate systems, unfortunate examination and oversight of schools and the negative discernment towards professional reflective development.

Additionally, the essential target of guaranteeing conveyance of value instruction and quality training and preparing, the Government will fortify the ongoing examination framework by expanding the recurrence of investigation of schools and organizations (no less than twice per school or establishment per term) with an exceptional spotlight on the nature of administration, the board, instructing, the growing experience and student accomplishment; creating and carrying out an instruction and preparing appraisal strategy at all levels that coordinates advancement of abilities and skills close by scholastic accomplishment in the eventual outcomes as well as enrolment of instructors, educator teachers, coaches and speakers to satisfy the set guidelines of Pupil Teacher Ratio (PTR). Other than the PTR, more spotlight should be on the appraisal and estimation apparatuses of value instructing to reinforce the holes in confirmed information on calling capabilities in educating.

To improve education standards at the neighborhood level, educational authorities collaborate with local stakeholders, sub-provincial, and regional officials. All schools are supposed to be assessed consistently by evaluators outside the school. The fundamental motivation behind this expert help Supervision and the general equilibrium of progress exercises are to work on the nature of instruction. The DES Inspection Instrument goes quite far to supplement crafted by the school improvement arranging to develop the conveyance of nature of training by empowering organizations to distinguish moves and lay proper techniques to defeat such difficulties.

Here below is the quality assurance and improvement activities carried out by the national inspectorate with their counterparts in related activities carried out at local government and school level.

Fig 2 Support Supervision Framework for Quality Improvement (DES, 2012)

Figure 2 above shows how Inspection takes place within a nationally established system and it is not an activity which any individual or group can just decide to carry out by themselves. The activity of inspection is overseen by the Ministry of Education. The ministry ensures that school inspections are carried out by the district education officers by ensuring that the school administrators have carried out School performance reviews and school improvement plans and give support supervision and strengthen profession reflection of the class teachers for improvements in learners' learning.

➤ *The Public Procurement and Disposal of Assets (PPDA) Implementation guidelines*

At the school level, these guidelines promote effective support supervision through audits and other monitoring mechanisms. All grade schools consent by submitting reports toward the start of every scholastic year by 30th of January to the DEOs who later submit to their particular nearby government specialists (CAOs) the endorsed financial plan gauges and work plans. The yearly work plans and school financial plans should cover the synopsis of accomplishments and difficulties in the past scholastic year and arranged exercises (presentation), School Improvement plans, designs/agenda on work plans and progress reports.

CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Introduction

A review of the literature is an evaluation of the data presented by many academics and researchers that is pertinent to the subject under investigation, "The influence of Support Supervision on Quality Education". In order to help the researcher fill in any gaps and advance the body of knowledge, this chapter offers literature based on research problems and hypotheses that have previously been addressed. In order to grasp and appreciate the information gaps addressed in the body of literature review, the issues of this investigation gave direction. The study's unique aims were taken into consideration when reviewing the literature.

B. Support Supervision and Quality of Primary School Education

One of the top initiatives in Uganda's bid to raise educational standards is support supervision through school inspection (DES, 2012). Other observers have typically been enthusiastic about the school inspection process for raising standards. Bennett (1978) communicated worry about the absence of systemic detail. Bennett contended that absence of systemic detail in school examination made it hard to evaluate the unwavering quality of the investigation discoveries. For example, the school Inspection framework in England turned into a question of much more noteworthy public and expert interest since its privatization because of the training Schools Act 1992 which is presently integrated in the school Inspections Act 1996 as per research studies (Matthews & Holmes et al.,2010).

Since the country's educational system was first established during British colonial control, there has been a school investigation administration in Uganda. The probe of elementary schools was managed on a territorial basis up until 1989, with District-based inspectors conducting inspections in nearby schools. The Ministry of Public Service's most recent study on the post-protected change reconstruction of the Ministry of Education and Sports (MoES) archive from 1998 recommended the establishment of an Education Standards Agency (ESA) to take the place of the Inspectorate.

The Inspectors of School make an intentional visit to grade schools where a free and outer assessment of the nature of training is given and explored. Outer assessment is the review by the DES and their partners while inner assessment is done inside the school organization and the head educators to screen or self-assess for development for incorporation in school improvement plans. Be that as it may, a few individual schools observe it by trying to acquire the certainty to attempt self-assessment without help of the public authority authorities from the service of instruction essential training division or Directorate body. The grade school Inspection (outside assessment) assumes a significant part in approving schools' self-assessment, alluding to public benchmarks.

To begin with, schools complete school preliminary exercises in preparation for assessment by checking themselves against Indicators from the Handbook for School Inspection and they incorporate:i) Quality of Teacher's Planning: for example linkage between example plans, plans of work and public educational programme prerequisites, with significant instructing and learning assistants; ii)Quality of purpose of assets and the homeroom climate, for example accessibility, adequacy, propriety of instructing and learning materials; iii) Quality of the Teaching and Learning process, for example, lucidity of direction of the illustration and instructor show; iv) Assessment and record keeping, for example, the degree to which a scope of appraisal strategies is actually used to assess the results of instructor and cycle learning; v) Teacher information, for example, certainty of the educator with the subject information instructed; vi) Pupils' getting it and accomplishment, for example students' fulfilment in education and numeracy; vii) School board and administration, for example, believability and regard of the head instructor and school executives locally; viii) Financial administration, for example, nature of planning, account keeping, monetary announcing, straightforwardness and responsibility; and ix) Management of assets, for example, accessibility and culmination on inventories.

As indicated by Monitoring and Supporting Policy, the school Inspectors do four (4) kinds of full investigations on each school and they incorporate; one time per year; short/routine reviews once a term, flying visits impromptu and follow-up examinations in something like a year and a half from when an assessment would be finished. Also, the Inspectors consider the adequacy of the inward assessment completed by schools while thinking about the nature of administration and the board inside the school.

Coming up next are the teacher performance indicators evaluated during the management of educating and learning. They incorporate: example lesson plans, records of work and educational programme inclusion, the schedule execution, evaluation, Head instructor's contribution in homeroom educating and Classroom oversight by head educator and other mindful staff individuals, following and investigation of students' exhibition, consistency standards and participation, Examination of students' advancement and other key information talked about in School Management Committee/Board of Governors and Parents and Teachers Association (PTA) gatherings. Guardians as individuals from the local area add to the nature of instruction when they take part in school gatherings in schools where their youngsters go. All conversations in reports are observed to illuminate strategy choices at the school board level for School executives and administration like believability and regard of the head instructor and school board locally.

Administration alludes to establishments and elements through which the schooling system apportions jobs and obligations, decides needs and plans, and completes instruction projects and approaches. By and large, quality improvement is the general need of the Ministry of Education and Sports (MoES, 2012).

➤ *Effective Support Supervision*

Support supervision is considered as one of effective improvement activities done during school investigation as indicated in inspectors' report (MoES,2012).

Effective support supervision refers to the extent to which support supervision activities improve the quality of primary education by providing guidance, supervision feedback and support to teachers during and after supervision of teaching.

In Uganda, school review is pointed toward giving public affirmation about the nature of training all over the nation; and to add to enhancements in instruction at the degree of individual schools, inside sub-provinces and regions and the nation overall. Public affirmation implies that reviewers have an obligation to give exact, far-reaching and dependable data, knowledge and information about the nature of instruction in individual schools and the nation as a whole.

Revealing is a critical part of the review interaction. There is no point in the examination occurring on the off chance that the discoveries are not conveyed obviously, precisely and on schedule: to head instructors, staff and different partners as both an oral report and a composed rundown report, to assist them with working on their school; and to DES local workplaces and headquarter as a formal composed report, on what you have found in a specific school, area or district, as open confirmation of the nature of training. The DES Inspectors give precise, far-reaching and solid data, insight and information about the nature of instruction in individual schools and the nation at large as indicated by Part 6: How we Inspect Guide (MoES, 2012).

School investigation further develops schools. Schools come out better as a spot for youngsters when the climate is protected and helpful. The necessities and privileges of youngsters are generally vital and the expert conduct of instructors to satisfy their most noteworthy guidelines for quality student results. The security of students is guaranteed for more joyful learning and subsequently quality improvement in their learning results as indicated by the Ministry of Education and Sports Guide Part 1: How can we improve our school (2012).

School Inspection gives applicable data that can be utilized in decision making for the World Bank and other giver accomplices particularly on the holes that might require prompt remedy for quality improvement in instruction. This infers the requirement for sound political and institutional examinations, considering the motivating forces looked by authorities and instructors to work on the nature of educating and learning; for reinforced responsibility and management frameworks that cover learning results in distraught school network. The World Bank (2006) suggests developing more advanced monitoring and assessment frameworks that track learning outcomes among different income and demographic groups over a specific period. These frameworks should cover staff and system performance, not just input and output measures, and include incentives to ensure that the findings are used in decision-making.

Preferably, oversight, through supporting educators, controlling schools' working and considering customary trades between schools, can be an amazing asset for quality improvement. Be that as it may, this is seldom the situation in Africa, likely even less so than somewhere else as indicated by research done on school oversight in Africa (De Grauwe, 2001; Diarra et al., 1997; Garforth, 2004; Gumbi and Dlamini, 1997; Lugaz et al., 2006; Solaux, 1997) showed the absence of fulfilment among instructors and managers with the effect of oversight on the homeroom (De Grauwe, 2007).

➤ *Methodology and Tools*

Moreover, the school's assessment procedure and instruments of section 6: How we investigate schools, incorporate execution pointers, quality markers and insight measures and principles (MoES, 2012). Instructor markers depend on the expert set of principles and the capabilities evaluated specified in the profile for essential educators (2005) and other report following organizations on the nature of educating (MoES,2019).

Authoritatively, when individual schools attempt self-assessment, they compose reports in view of the strategy and the apparatuses to gather the confirmed information composed gives an account of qualities and shortcomings as well as information on self-assessment with respect to the foundation and its head instructor or head. All the more in this way, suitable measures on these particular homeroom training and instructor documentation would give pertinent data to direct further examination reads up, for example the Factors that might be influencing the act of intelligent instructing in Uganda's essential schooling so that the holes therein can be reinforced to further develop showing quality and learning results. In this manner, the information gathered on unambiguous educator pointers for further developed execution should be fortified. It is expressed that the fact that there is a strategy in the head educator's office does not imply that what it says is really working out. Whenever the reviewer or head instructor assesses the nature of a part of training given by the school, one ought to distinguish every Quality Indicator, momentarily compose notes about the qualities and shortcomings noticed, and base on the proof assembled while the central issues are to be recorded on educating and the viewpoints which influence students noticed.

Notwithstanding, the idea of the apparatuses used to acquire quality educator markers and learning results impact the strategy choice on the improvement of other arrangement mediations. For instance, the Bank ought to require all new Country Assistance Strategies to incorporate learning results markers (World Bank, 2006). Consequently, there is a mismatch with what the instruments are expected to gauge because of the idea of the reports gave in the information framework.

The rules "By they way we assess" express that an auditor does not have to note proof against each subject: Quality Indicators are not agendas. A portion of the proof might connect with information accumulated, some to interviews (casual visits as well as formal gatherings) and some to perceptions made; the significance of every one of the qualities and regions for development ought to be thought of. The Inspector then requests that the instructors reflect for each situation whether they have adversely affected the nature of students' encounters and accomplishments; and afterward at last concludes whether the nature of the viewpoint assessed is excellent, great, feeble or poor, utilizing the graph on Page 14 of how we examine norms. This is an expert judgement in the light of the significance of the proof noticed and the degree to which specific elements adversely affect youngsters' learning, wellbeing, joy or accomplishments. Along these lines, on the off chance that noticed information is not given in that frame of mind to direct the approach interaction, it turns out to be hard for strategy entertainers to pursue informed choices in view of the issues recognized in educating. Subsequently, it becomes difficult to obtain details of a particular issue if the apparatus used is not appropriate.

With regard to gathering information, the seen/not seen approach has significant constraints when it is utilized as an investigation apparatus as it does not resolve issues of value with regard to showing quality for worked-on Quality Education. For instance, the presence of illustration plans is less significant than whether example arranging is utilized really to further develop learning. Instructors might create illustration plans, yet these might be of low quality or not really be applied while educating, which is many times the situation. Educators may in some cases basically produce example intents to be seen by ranking directors or outside evaluators, and it very well may be too hard to separate between a viable and inadequate instructor. As a guideline, while searching for narrative proof among the instructors, the "What and how" educators really instruct is a higher priority than their message put down for examiners to check out. Information on Quality Education ponders more the learning results as opposed to the quality contributions of the educators that add to Quality Education. Also, information is not completely accessible on Uganda's Education measurements (Uganda Education Statistical Abstract, 2009).

There is likewise a test with the apparatus being used in the light of the fact that when one makes assessments on the nature of educating and learning, the manager will review the Quality Indicator connected with the nature of initiative. Additionally, while assessing the students' achievement in class work and assessments, one needs to review Quality Indicators connected with the nature of instructing. Yet, where could the quality marks of instructing be? How are showing quality pointers examined in Quality Education? This is on the grounds that measurable information on learning results has been given in information base not at all like the educating quality. But it is expressed that these connections are causal. The bungle in the estimation of student results and evaluation on quality educating has additionally augmented the holes in instructing rehearses. For instance: If students' achievement is poor, how then can educating and it be assessed as great to learn processes?

These inquiries have not been obviously replied by the examiners. Subsequently, irregularities in the device use and absence of explicit instruments of intelligent educating to assess showing quality markers have hampered the strategy cycle of concocting the right mediation measures on reinforcing instructing rehearses.

The improvement of the apparatuses for reflection is propelled by the humanistic area by Michel Foucault. Humanistic trainers(educators) offer a few tasks to students to help their course investment and have the option to investigate their arrangement of values, desires, potential outcomes and obligations to foster one's life and meet their objectives (Sonneveld,2013).

The Inspectors' lead is likewise required in the system to be straightforward, freely accessible and imparted to school staff. This is basically on the grounds that the singular perspectives on those talked with stay private except if they show that the wellbeing of certain students might be in danger (MoES, 2010).

C. Stakeholders' Responsibilities and Quality of Primary Education

The inspectors develop attitudes and behaviours that enable them to focus on bringing about improvement for the sake of the children in schools. In particular, being honest, impartial and having a sense of integrity in their practice help them to develop the kinds of relationships with teachers and leaders in schools and districts to enable them become constructive and persuasive when providing feedback, while also remaining firm and focused above all on what is best for the school generally.

A number of stakeholders include the Directorate of Education Standards and KCCA, Senior Education officers, assistant Education officers, Inspectors of school, Local council, members of the Board of Governors, parents, etc.

The Senior Education officers address issues of quality Education, quality teaching, and other issues related to behaviour of school staff like absenteeism etc. The Senior Education officers as assigned by the Education Commissioner internalize and implement guidelines and policies, circulars issued by the Ministry of Education and Sports and as disseminated and explained by

the District Education Office. School inspection reports are discussed with staff, and then corrective actions for interventions are subsequently followed up. According to Danim (2005), the chief determinant of teacher involvement and raising the standard of learning processes and outcomes is the principal's (head teacher) ability to lead. The principal or head teacher is the most crucial element when assessing whether instructors as well as other school staff are able to function at their best. Therefore, the ability of the head teacher to guide and motivate the teacher will have a considerable impact on the achievement of the quality of learning at the school level. It is also acknowledged that positioned school leaders need to adopt an attitude and mentality that aims to develop distributed leadership capacity inside their institution, enabling others to take the reins of leadership (Morgan, 2008; Ross, Lutfi, & Hope, 2016).

Additionally, the school is responsible for its performance. According to research studies, it was shown that effective schools make a difference based on the outcomes that are consistently tied to changes in the school's environment, culture, or ethos and school culture that can be changed by the school staff working together (Gibson & Asthana, 2006).

More so, the senior Education Officers under the oversight of Board of Governors/ School Management Committee prepare for inspection scheduled at least twice per term and produce reports which are submitted monthly to the District Education Officers (DEO) as well as appraisal annual reports. It is also the teachers' responsibility to follow the Education Notice, 2012.

The Procurement and Disposal Entities (PDEs) are fully centralized and under Central Government make quarterly reports through their governing bodies to the Accounting Officers (Head teachers) of MoES in respective formats set out in the Procurement and Disposal of Public Assets (PPDA) Guidelines, No.5 (2014).

All activities carried out by the Ministry of Education and Sports are governed by the Education Sector Strategic Plans (ESSP) 2004-2005/ESSP 2017/18-2019/20. The mission of the Ministry is to "support, guide, coordinate, oversee and encourage Quality Education and Sports to everyone in Uganda for National Integration, Individual and National Development." The goal of the Education Sector Strategic Plan is to assist the Ministry in carrying out this mandate. To conduct educational programmes that require shared leadership duties in order to realize the joint objective of high-quality primary education, the MoES gave various groups, including ESA, KYU, and TIET, among other educational organizations, a mandate.

Guidelines for Districts and Urban Councils (2008) on Policy, Planning, Roles, and Duties of Partners in the Delivery of Universal Primary Education (UPE) are also available. The goals of Annex 5 were to: (i) establish, provide, and maintain high-quality education as the cornerstone for fostering the development of human resources; (ii) transform society in a fundamentally positive way; (iii) provide the bare minimum of resources and amenities to allow every child to enrol in school and stay there until the initial cycle of schooling is finished; and (iv) enable the government to carry out its duty to end illiteracy while giving every individual the opportunity to pursue their own education development. Make sure that Basic Education is available to students, pertinent to their requirements, and in line with overall national objectives. However, there is still considerable work to be done to enhance the equal availability of excellent and pertinent schooling and sports if the nation's school system is to stay up with labour market demands and global developments (ESSP FY 2017/18 - 2019/20).

The Ministry of Education issues standards required to support the professional code of conduct of the observed teacher. The professional standards have a range of professional skills, attitudes and experience, which are generic and related to the work of all professionals and civil servants. Professional expertise is specific to the work of inspectors' broader experience, on which inspectors can build, for example from their previous teaching experience or even their non-professional lives, and leadership skills to help them take leading roles in improving education across the country. According to Sallis (2011), it is the duty of the leader in charge to raise the standard of instruction and to assist all teachers and other educational staff in carrying out the leader's developed strategic actions.

According to UNICEF (2019), a supportive supervision system in this case should at the very least incorporate the following ideas: an explicit comprehension of roles and expected contributions, teaching with praise, acknowledging positive contributions, advice on how to handle challenging situations, and a strategy that uses a circular feedback process to provide skills, tools, and solutions to problems.

Additionally, policymakers such as Ministers and government officials are responsible for engaging in long-term strategic planning for education across the country. There are several teams from various institutions ranging from international development partners and agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and organizations responsible for teacher education and other aspects of educational provision and improvement; school administrators, parents and community members have an entitlement to information about the calibre of education offered by the schools to which they send their children. Members of the public, including taxpayers and employers are all entitled to know whether taxes are being used effectively to provide education of good quality and whether young people who leave school have the necessary knowledge and skills that are employable. Lastly, if learners themselves have a right to know if the education in the school which they attend compares well with national standards and to standards in other similar institutions (MoES, 2012).

The Ministry of Education and Sports acts as a Sector Wide Approach (SWAp) co-ordinating centre with the goal to carry out the Evaluation and Monitoring portion of the System. In order to achieve this, it identifies the informational requirements of all decision-makers, disseminates that information via comprehensive reporting channels, and makes sure that those requirements are rapidly and effectively met. Monitoring and evaluation frameworks are used to keep track on the primary strategic sector objectives of access, fairness, excellence, and effectiveness (ESSP FY 2017/18 - 2019/20).

The MoES's teacher policy reforms are based on the government's White Paper on Education (1992), which was prepared. Chapter 8 of the Government White Paper on Education (1992) focuses mostly on teachers and teacher education. It is abundantly obvious that the Government is aware of the vital leadership and service roles that educators play in implementing programmes and regulations, as well as the importance that must be placed on the calibre of its educators (Para 382). By fostering a sense of collaboration between the teaching profession and the school, teachers can help students develop their desire for and capacity for learning (Ref. Paras. 383–384).

D. Mentorship Support and Quality of Primary Education

Tutoring is the best instrument for supporting the nature of execution of instructors. Coaching in Teacher schooling is a quality affirmation process inside the wide comprehension of complete quality administration with its many advantages for instructive organizations. Tutoring has likewise turned into a significant piece of instructor training, as a component of both the improvement of intelligent practice and the professional progress of educational institutions (Sundli, 2007). Experienced and beginning educators, Burgess and Mayes (2007); Hurd, Jones, McNamara and Craig (2007); and Remington Smith (2007) propose a path of cooperative inquiry to explore and foster ideas on insightful practice. Tutoring in this setting means to invigorate appearance in this recommended course of proceeding with common request. Reflection can in this way be utilized to work with understudies' advancement of an expert character (Korthagen, 2004; Pavlovich, 2007).

Reflection on effective practice, according to Seferolu (2006) and Wilson and Demetriou (2007), is one of the qualities that characterize a good educator. It follows that improving values, knowledge, and skills that encourage reflective thinking about education is one of the ways a prospective instructor might develop into a successful educator. This means that instructor teachers (coaches) must create opportunities and facilitate interactions that will encourage the educators' capacity to reflect on their training. Korthagen (2004) contemplates the fundamental characteristics of a decent educator and asks how understudies can turn out to be great instructors. Different examinations have moved toward this inquiry according to an authoritative viewpoint, including the college (Schulze, 2003) as well as the school (Quick and Siebörger, 2005; Schulman & Schulman, 2004), and considering the educator as tutor (Burgess & Mayes, 2007; Edwards & Collinson, 1996).

According to Kram (1985), in order for a tutoring relationship to be successful, mentees must be open to the strategy and make it a point to comprehend what the mentor offers to the discussion. As a result, the apprentice must revere, respect, and emulate their instructor. The mentee's relationship with and imitation of the mentor is intended to help the mentee develop positive attitudes and behaviours, learn how rude and unhelpful behaviour can stifle enthusiastic development, and set academic and professional goals.

There are likewise five phases connected with the most common way of forming a coach instructor programme in schools today as per Sindelar (1992). They include framing a reasoning, picking tutors and protégés, creating guides, observing the coaching system and assessing and looking into the programme. Best practices have been created concerning mentorship programmes. Also, there has been an explanation that school-based realistic parts and cycles matter including: i) choice of coaches with a similar affirmation and in closeness to their necessities, ii) arrangement of tutors and mentees' plans that permit normal arranging time and valuable chances to notice one another, iii) decreased responsibilities for mentees, and iv) arrangement of directions for the two guides and mentees (Flynn & Nolan, 2008, pp.173-174).

Mentorship helps the mentee to relate to and impersonate the guide, get support for positive ways of behaving and mentalities, figure out how pessimistic and unseemly ways of behaving may impede enthusiastic development, and create instructive and work objectives. Educator learning is the course of reflection and activity through which instructors foster abilities, and gain information and aptitude (Billet, 2001 in Wilson and Demetriou, 2007:214).

For this situation, individual schools from each locale need to guarantee that mentorship programmes for essential educators are given. DES auditors with a scope of expert abilities, mentalities and experience, some of which cross over, need to give mentorship programmes. At first, a mentorship programme is one of the techniques and a component of School execution surveys that furnish essential educators with the intelligent abilities and information to find success and stay dynamic in the calling.

Barrera et al. (2009) made sense that mentorship programmes are expected to be analysed intermittently to survey the degree to which their necessities are agreeably met to start instructors.

E. School Performance Reviews and Quality of Primary Education

Investigation finishes into the development of School Performance Reviews (SPR).

School Performance Reviews is a methodology to improve viable institutional/school arranging by fortifying intelligent practice among the staff (MoES, 2010). Instructors have a Professional obligation to give sufficient opportunity to their obligations as is expected by the idea of their calling. This would offer instructors chance to ponder their own training and have the option to self-assess their educating and rehearses (Tucker, Stronge, and Gareis, 2002).

Outreach guides in Core Primary Teachers' Colleges support instructors and go to lead School Performance Reviews. That is, the effort guides support head educators to foster everyday schedule, direct self-assessment and evaluation during School Performance Reviews. Examiners are energized to follow examinations by getting back to schools to check whether upgrades have been made since the past investigation. All the more along these lines, to add to upgrades in training at the degree of individual schools, inside sub-regions and locales and the nation overall, there are numerous manners by which reviewers add to progress in schools and areas. During Inspection action, assessors interface with head instructors, advanced staff, class educators, students and individuals from the local area. Educators are posed inquiries which urge them to ponder their own training and the nature of instruction given by their school and to consider how both of these can be improved (MoES, 2012).

Outer assessment directs the improvement cycle, covering self-assessment and evaluation during School Performance Reviews as a significant part of a school's responsibility to its partners. Inside assessment includes all individuals from the school local area: head educators and staff, overseeing bodies, Foundation bodies, parent agents and youngsters themselves. Moreover, the customary continuous assessment of this sort is much of the time called 'checking' and is fully backed up by neighborhood government assessors, planning focus mentors (CCTs) and, some of the time, particular NGOs with proficient instruction staff prepared in evaluative strategies.

Likewise, the Acts, Policy Guidelines and Regulations Handbook (MoES (2010) involves strategy changes expected to work on Quality of Education administration arrangement among which the schools are supposed to complete self-assessment as a component of the course of School Performance Review and School Improvement Planning. Educators utilize a self-evaluation instrument to rate their exhibition, obligations/work capacities. The instructors evaluate their own training to figure out what is planned to be done, Analysis is really done, and Reflection on execution and reported plans for the subsequent stages are put to records. The estimation apparatus that surveys the instructor skills has a presentation rating on a size of 1-5, on the Percentage score and execution level. This Alludes to the Competence profile (2005) appraisal device for instructor capabilities. In any case, there is no factual information on the equivalent.

So, either the educator as a person or the school as a whole might be the subject of inspection. This distinction does not concern specifics: a focus on the teachers makes them accountable for quality as individuals, whereas a focus on the school recognizes the importance of its operations and of the collaborations between the head teachers and guardians (De Grauwe, 2007). To support the process of school improvement, quality is essential.

Both the quality cycle and the school improvement model make an effort to separate best practices. To quantify all upgrades, best practices are employed as a benchmark. The two approaches try to arrange authoritative practices with expected outcomes and educational goals. One of the key components of the two models is continuous improvement. According to Prestiadi, Zulkarnain, and Sumarsono (2019), the sole aspect of an administrative framework that can be used to carry out a school improvement model is quality.

Also, toward the finish of each investigation, monitors recognize qualities on which schools can construct and regions for development which help the strategy entertainers to think of fitting intercessions involved in the improvement plans.

Overseers likewise share instances of good practice across schools to broadly uphold upgrades more. Consequently, there is need for irrefutably factual measurable information to additionally illuminate global, public and nearby offices and associations with a transmit for instructive improvement, for instance advancement accomplices, the National Curriculum Development Centre, the Uganda National Examination Board and individual regions and districts during the public reports and introductions at gatherings and gatherings to illuminate approaches and have the option to distribute needs on execution rules or advancement of apparatuses to resolve the main things in need of attention inside help management.

All the more, in this way, research on school evaluation suggests that evaluators should adopt a multi-layered approach to gather data on school and teacher effectiveness. Studies by Beerens (2000), Danielson and McGreal (2000), Johnson (1997), Kyriakides and Campbell (2004), and Nevo (1995) recommend using various methods to collect and analyze data, including classroom observations, student assessments, and feedback from teachers and other stakeholders.

The examiners likewise trade data with Centre Coordinating Tutors (CCT) and with other region authorities so that each gathering is kept informed about the help needs of individual schools, and know about the parts of enhancement for which individual schools are presently locked in. Group working between regional authorities and CCTs is fundamental for upgrades in schools, especially in essential training, to be upheld and maintained. For upgrades in schools, investigators need to persistently think about and work on the nature of their own review practice, model the course of progress for schools and areas.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Introduction

The framework of methodology was employed to comprehend the variables influencing the efficacy (validity and reliability) of our method(s). The mixed approach, a recently created research methodology, was utilized in this study to promote the methodical integrating, or "mixing," of both qualitative and quantitative information within a single inquiry or continuous programme of inquiry. The key principle of this approach is that integration allows for greater accuracy and complementary use of data than separate qualitative and quantitative information collection and analysis. The "mixed methods" methodology of this study integrated data, analysed the collected data from both the documents reviewed and the e-questionnaire tool and hard copies. These enabled the analysis on the objectives for the study on support supervision for improved quality education.

B. Study Design

Cross-sectional research was used to gather information only from the different sub-groups of people in the Education Sector, who differ in years of practice in supervising and supporting reflective practice with other characteristics such as their level of education, supervision skills and tool use for evidenced data on the same. In this study, the survey research design was used to assess the level of support supervision carried out by the stakeholders to enhance quality education through Reflective practice.

C. Area of Study

The study's focus was on how Support Supervision affected Quality Education as an improvement activity. Today's low-quality education is a result of the instructors' low-quality contributions. It goes without saying that effective educators give their students rich, engaging, and organized learning opportunities. The chances offered by their occupation and the community's recognition of their achievements benefit teachers who provide these possibilities. So, if teachers in primary schools are given significant Support of mentorship on teaching reflectively, they would be able develop creative and critical skills, and reflective skills that would enable them achieve SDG 4 and the goals of the Education Sector Strategy for Uganda's quality of primary school education.

D. Information Sources

The study collected data from secondary as well as primary sources. Unfiltered, first-hand information from the research area was provided by primary sources. The handing out of questionnaires served as the main source of information for this research. The secondary sources of information for the study included books, journal papers, websites for government publications, and a written review checklist.

➤ Primary Data

Primary data are the factual, first-person narratives of a study that are written by the individual who performs the study or is involved in it. A statement of the law from a governmental body, such as an executive agency, the President, or the Governor, is another example of primary data. Primary data in this study was basically obtained through personal e-questionnaire (structured) with respondents from the sample of MoES, the DES supervisors and Education Officers from the District and Educators in TIET, Directorate Education KCCA, and Inspectors of school overall responsible for supervision of the primary teachers. Other primary data used was obtained from policy frameworks. These include: The Inspection framework and teacher assessment tools of reflective practice, The Government White Paper and The Education Act 2008, including UPE policy and other teacher policies that were thought to have provisions related to the study.

➤ Secondary Data

An examination and interpretation of initial research are referred to as secondary data. It also refers to materials that discuss, clarify, interpret, and analyse the various teacher and education policies that are currently in effect or that should be, such as the competence profile for primary school teachers in Uganda, policy reviews from the Uganda Education White Paper of 1992, and the Education Sector Strategic Plan (ESSP) 2017–2019–20, UPE policy brief and TIET teacher policy reforms and The Education Act 2008, Education Service Act 2002, Legal notice supplements 2012 and other research papers in line with teacher issues. In-depth citations to original legal materials and other pertinent secondary sources are also offered by secondary sources. In this study, secondary data were gathered through secondary sources, such as manuals, papers, publications, policy frameworks, and internet use. These sources provided the raw data, which was then compiled, paraphrased, quoted, and analysed.

E. Population and Sampling Techniques

Purposive sampling was used in this study to randomly select participants who were both professional men and women from multiple sites in charge of UPE including: Directorate Education Standards (DES), Basic Education Department (BED), Directorate education KCCA, DIS, TEDT, and Basic Education Standards, Teacher Education Development Training (TEDT) and District Education Officers (DEOs) and school administrators with the most information on the characteristic of interest and from where 100 respondents were selected.

➤ *Sample size determination*

One hundred and six (106) people who work for the various institutions mentioned above made up the study's sample size. Yamane's formulas were used to calculate the sample size from the 145-person research population, as follows: where n is the sample size, N is the population size, and e is the level of significance, which is set at 0.05. According to figure 4.1, out of the 100 participants in this study, 66% were men and 34% were women.

F. Variables and Indicators

The variables that were used in this study included concepts of Support Supervision and Quality Education. The indicators of support supervision as an independent variable explain the variation in the outcome of Quality of Education. For example: Quality indicators and standards of teaching and learning; mentorship which includes Follow-up and feedback, skills and know how; School performance Reviews include tools used to collect data, School and teacher assessments and reflective practice; and shared roles and responsibilities by the body of inspectors or Actors that influence Quality Education.

G. Measurement Levels

This study used frequency to analyse elements that included demographic characteristics like respondents' age, years of experience on start of supervision, their department/role, reflective practice and School Performance Reviews and Mentorship Support; while mean, standard deviation were used to analyse responses on the effectiveness of School Inspection, and stakeholders' responsibilities; and Bi-variate analysis of two variables using chi-square test to determine the level of significance between Support Supervision and Quality Education; and Association between Supervisor's Responsibilities and Quality of Education. Also, Likert scale questions were given to participants and multiple responses that were categorical and numerical in nature were collected.

H. Procedure for Data Collection

The proposal was submitted to the Faculty of Social Sciences and presented UCU–Research Ethical Committee for academic defence and it was successfully approved after its presentation; later provided a compliance report to the UCU-REC on agreed upon areas of improvement. The researcher obtained a cover letter from the University authorizing her to conduct the research on the UCU-REC approval to conduct research in the designated field. A prior visit (reconnaissance) to Ministry of Education and Sports was conducted to ascertain the field conditions and consent with the authorities so as to make contact with the respondents especially the key informants from the different departments such as DES, BES, Directorate Education, KCCA, TEDT, DEOs, school administrators, UPE schools in Kampala. The Key informants were given the online questionnaire tool on consent that they would participate in an ongoing research study. Also, a call away was necessary for the participants, especially those who opted for online tool in order to consent and provide responses to the questions provided in the questionnaire as needed.

The E-questionnaire tool was used to collect raw data that was both quantitative (close-ended) and qualitative (open-ended). The e-questionnaire was used because of the Standard Operating Procedures that have been put in place due to COVID -19 pandemic. A set of raw data was captured on Google forms that were linked to the E-questionnaire while another set of raw data was captured on hard copies of the questionnaires, especially for those who opted for offline questionnaire. After data collection, Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) software was opened where quantitative data was entered.

However, as was already indicated, descriptive data analysis was not performed using NVivo because SPSS offers more methods for screening or purging data in advance of further analysis. In this regard, a database was established based on the pre-coded questionnaire that was available both online and in print copy. Each answer to the question was given a code, and a coding sheet was created using the matching numbers. When entering data into the database, references were made to the sheets with the codes for the various questionnaire items. The variables were computed generating the outputs, cleaning the data and analysing it focusing on the key areas of support supervision and reflective practice in the profession, and other related policy issues that affect support supervision.

I. Data Collection Instruments

The data was collected using the e-questionnaire tool and documentary checklist review. The choice of these tools were considered because of the effects of COVID- 19. However, for those who opted for hard copies of the questionnaires, they were availed to them physically to fill in their responses. The primary data which was found existing in both the reviewed documents and the e-questionnaires were then coded for the analysis to ascertain their adequacy given on the influence of support supervision on Quality Education. Two cross-sectional survey methods were important in the collection of primary data gotten from the Ministry of Education and Sports participants and online Library research.

➤ *Questionnaire*

The questionnaire consisted of open-ended and closed-ended questions that enabled collection of feedback (raw data) from the respondents. These questions were all modified in accordance with the research questions for data collection purpose. They were adapted from the Support Supervision Book Module 4 (WHO, 2008); The 7th Edition of Introducing Public administration (Shafritz, Russel, Borick, 2011); The Supervisor Handbook (Physicians); Browse Supervisor Self-Reflection and Skills Review Tool at (www.racp.edu.au) and Celes (2010).

The questionnaire tool had 28 questions under the theme of Support Supervision and Quality Education. The Stakeholders' years of experience in supervision by distribution ranged from 1 to 25+ years. Their years of experience in supervising reflective practices were categorized: i) those who were in the ranges of 1-5 years, 6-10 years and 11-25+ years. Their academic levels included: the Diploma, BA ED/BED degrees, the MA ED/MED degree, and PhD holders. The professionals included officials from the DES, BES/MoES, and DEOs, Education Directorate KCCA and other key informants from TEDT and NCDC, Kampala.

➤ *Documentary Review Checklist*

Document inspection is a technique for social research and a type of qualitative research in which the researcher interprets official and scholarly documents to provide a voice and meaning to a topic under evaluation.

To support the primary source from the field and support result interpretation and discussion in this study, the resource information from the online library's primary and secondary sources was read and analysed. These documents included: reports, articles, journals and books, the education policies for teachers, international instruments, and other research papers. This study was also aided by library research, which provided the primary and secondary data required for it. The e-documents contained the following: the ESA Inspection Framework, the Education Act of 2008, the UPE policy of 2014, the Acts, Policy Guidelines and rules Handbook on Teachers/Instructor/Tutor Education and Training Policies, and the laws, policies, investment plans, rules, strategies, and program for the education sector (Annex 5), Uganda Government White Paper 1992, Teacher policy and guidelines in the National Teacher policy, Part 3: How well are our learners doing? , Part 1: How can we improve our school, From Educational Access to Learning Outcomes: An Unfinished Agenda, the Primary Teachers Competency Profile, Report on Basic Education Sector Analysis, performance of KCCA-Education in Q3, 2019 KCCA Statistical Abstract, 2019/20 Budgeting and Implementation Guidelines for Primary and Secondary, 2019 ESSPR Annual Performance Report, Ugandan and Sub-Saharan African Teacher Issues, DFID Education policy reforms Uganda 1997-2004, e-books that provide evidenced data on the policy reforms and improvement activities for improving teacher quality within the Education Sector. Other primary data was provided: MoES Basic Education Standards such as SPRs C-TEP documents to read and analyse them to ascertain their adequacy given on their effectiveness in implementing reflective practices for teachers. Two cross-sectional survey methods were used in the collection of primary data. They include online questionnaires and online Library research.

J. Quality/Error control

A measure's ability to measure what it is intended to assess is known as measurement validity. There would be systematic bias or inaccuracy in the measuring method and the collected data if an indicator were to be invalid. The e-questionnaire tool was self-administered to test reliability. It was then shared with the supervisor for review and purposes of informed consent and recommendation as an ethical requirement and a means to ensure that the tool respects the dignity of research participants. It was then piloted to a non-targeted population sample of professionals in the education sector or teacher institutions to test if the predicted desired results could be obtained. After undergoing the process of its validity, it was shared purposively to the key persons in the decentralized sub-groups from DES, MoES/BES and district education offices and Directorate Education KCCA and others. The responses (raw data) from the primary and secondary sources were collected and tested using statistical tests to estimate policy impacts based upon quantitative or statistical analysis to understand the specific issue, and eliminate generalization of personalized views of the researcher. The relevant literature obtained in this study was quoted to back up evidence and as well avoid plagiarism. In order to comprehend the context in which the study was done and to draw accurate and trustworthy conclusions and feedback, summaries were contextualized based on observations and perceptions and then coupled with policy analyses. Murphy and Dingwall (2003) correctly noted that following processes by themselves is not enough to provide reliable outcomes, but this does not imply that procedures can be disregarded. Additionally, reliability and validity difficulties need to be taken into account when reading or developing research initiatives.

K. Strategy for Data Processing and Analysis

The documents were reviewed and summarized according to each objective of this study. The specific data for each objective of this study were coded; grouped manually, evaluated and revised to ensure that the needed information from the given objectives had sufficient evidence to back up the study. Thematic analysis was used to analyse participant responses from the survey. By using the different themes, the study analysed and reported patterns and observations from the participants, given that there was a small sample size, the themes to summarize results and to connect back to the research question.

Then the narrative was written to describe and explain data and back up the evidence in line with the main objective. The MS Excel sheet was used to enter raw data for labelling and sorting. The MS Excel raw data in file was then imported into SPSS software for cleaning and analysis of quantitative data. The study then reported quantitative percentages from categorical data on the survey. The SPSS is an abbreviation for Statistical Package for Social Scientists. Data analysis using SPSS focused on multivariate analysis of independent variables of Support Supervision.

L. Anticipated Methodology Constraints

Mixed-methods research is more expensive than a single method approach in terms of time, resources and energy. This was solved by fully engaging in the study to accomplish the tasks of the study at hand.

Integrating both qualitative and quantitative data during the analysis phase was a challenge because it required technical expertise in the field of research. This was solved by looking out for one research expert who offered guidance on data sorting.

Some of the documents online needed to be purchased or required permission before having access. This was solved by accessing official documents that could be accessed publicly online and Google scholar and from the office of the MoES. In the long run, this improved the validity and reliability of the resulting data and strengthened the outcomes on variables that were correlated.

M. Timeline

The research study was carried out from 2019 to 2022.

Table 1 A Timetable Showing the Dates of Expected Completion of Various Sections of the Report

Concept Note	Research Proposal	Data collection	Data Analysis	Presentation of the Findings	Submission of the Dissertation
13th September 2019	30th June 2021	July 2021	August 2021	August 2021	April 2022

N. Ethical Approval

All required paperwork, data collection tools, and letters of consent utilized in the research study were ethically approved by the UCU Ethics Review Board. Also, consent was sought from the Directorate Education KCCA and MoES departments to allow me to collect data from the school inspectors to ensure that their personal views were not violated by the researcher. This was important for this study because of the human participants working whose issues or information that was shared needed to be protected as an observance of ethical code of conduct in research. This promoted the rights, safety and well-being of all participants involved in the study.

➤ Ethical issues

Ethical considerations observed as one of the main standards in research as per Bryman and Bell (2007) were as follows: i) Full assent was first gotten from the experts such as; Basic Education/MoES and Directorate Education KCCA preceding the review; ii) An adequate level of confidentiality for the exam data was ensured. The analyst adhered to confidentiality commitments and never disclosed identifiable information to third parties without members' consent. Thus, the promise of confidentiality was upheld and, as a result, this promise resulted in an obligation not to disclose information provided in confidence unless the confider consented to it; iii) Any ambiguity or distortion regarding the points and objectives of the investigation were avoided; iv) Any correspondence related to the investigation was completed honestly and openly; and v) Any kind of misleading information, as well as portrayal of crucial information, were avoided.

CHAPTER FOUR PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

A. Introduction

This chapter discusses, analyses, and interprets the findings regarding the roles of stakeholders and quality primary education, as well as teacher mentorship and quality education in schools. The presentation follows the following themes: school performance and quality primary education; school performance and mentorship support; and school inspection and quality primary education. The study's overarching goal was to examine the inadequacies in support supervision that were concentrated on the teachers' reflective practices and supported the implementation of quality enhancements in Ugandan primary school instruction. The introduction of the respondents' demographic data is followed by the findings related to the three exploration hypotheses. The review generated both subjective and objective data. The discoveries are displayed as structure recurrence counts, rates, tables, and figures, such as pie charts and visual diagrams. Following the results, analysis and interpretations are provided.

B. Response rate

The study looked to address the targets by overseeing a poll to respondents and dissecting it. Out of 106 respondents to whom the survey was directed, 100 respondents had the option to give criticism and presented the web-based polls and printed versions to the specialist. This addressed 94.2% reaction rate which is adequate from which to make inferences. Mugenda (2003) pronounces a half or more reaction rate as being agreeable to use in finishing up upon. The review considers 75% reaction rate as satisfactory, 60% or more as great, while 70% or more is excellent. Essentially, Babbie (2010) attested that return paces of above a half are adequate to break down and distribute, 60% is great and 70% is awesome. This implies that the reaction rate for this study being 100 per cent was awesome.

C. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Gender, age groups, educational attainment, departments, and roles within the department or directorate in supporting the implementation of UPE were among the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents in this study. Tables and figures are used to present the conclusions regarding these.

To ensure that both genders participated, the study determined the distribution of respondents depending on gender. Figure 3 presents the findings.

Fig 3 Gender Based Distribution of Respondents
Source: Primary data, 2022

In accordance with the results shown in Figure 3 above, this study had a higher proportion of male respondents than female respondents. Figure 4.2 shows that of the 100 responders, 66% were male and 34% were female.

➤ Respondents' Age

One objective of the study was to determine the distribution of ages of the survey respondents. The study's findings are depicted in Figure 4.2.

Fig 4 Age-Based Distribution of Respondents in Percentages
Source: Primary Data, 2022

Out of the 100 respondents who took part in the survey, 15% were between the ages of 20 and 29; 31% were between the ages of 30 and 39; 37% were between the ages of 40 and 49; while 17% were 50 years of age or above, according to the data in Figure 4.2 above. This shows that the majority of the sample (68%) consisted of participants who were 40 years of age or older.

➤ *Years of Practice Developing Reflective Teaching Methods*

The study determined the length of the respondents' involvement in advancing reflective teaching techniques. Figure 4.3 displays the results for these.

Fig 5 Distribution of Respondents by Year of Experience in Strengthening Reflective Teaching Practices
Source: Primary Data, 2022

Results in Figure 5 show that out of the 100 respondents who participated in this study, 18% of them had been involved in strengthening reflective teaching practices for between 1 and 5 years; 51% of the participants have involved in strengthening reflective teaching practices for between 6 to 10 years; and 31% of the respondents have been involved in strengthening reflective teaching practices for 11 years and above.

➤ *Level of Education*

The research determined the highest level of education of respondents as they engaged in strengthening reflective teaching practices. This was aimed at determining whether the respondents had knowledge and capacity that could help in strengthening reflective teaching practice. The findings regarding these are presented as shown in Figure 6

Fig 6 Distribution of Respondents Based on Education level
Source: Primary Data, 2022

Figure 6 reveals that out of the 100 respondents who took part in the study, 5% had a certificate, 15% had a diploma, 48% had a bachelor's degree, 26% had a Master's degree, and the remaining 6% had a PhD.

➤ *Respondents' Department from the Ministry of Education and Sports*

The respondents were asked to indicate the departments from the Ministry of Education they worked for. The findings concerning these are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents by their Respective Departments from MoES

Departments	Frequency	Percent
Directorate of Education Standards	15	15.0
Directorate Education KCCA	16	16.0
School administration	31	31.0
District Education Department	13	13.0
Basic Education Department	11	11.0
Local government	8	8.0
Others TEDT and NCDC	6	6.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Table 2's findings show that, of the 100 respondents who took part in the survey, 15% came from the Directorate of Education Standards; Directorate of Education Kampala City Council Authority (KCCA) accounted for 16% of the respondents, followed by 31% from UPE Schools, 13% from the District Education Department, 11% from the Department of Basic Education for Primary, 8% from the local government, and 6% from other departments like Teacher Education Development Training (TEDT) and National Curriculum Development.

➤ *Respondents' Roles from their Respective Departments*

The roles played by various respondents in their respective departments in fostering the implementation of UPE through reflective practice among different stakeholders were also established in this study. The findings concerning their roles are shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3 Distribution of Roles of the Respondents by their Departments

Roles	Frequency	Percent
Directorate officers	20	20.0
Inspectors of schools	17	17.0
Education Officers	21	21.0
Local government	6	6.0
Directorate Education KCCA Inspectors	12	12.0
Senior Education Officers	11	11.0
Assistant Education officers	9	9.0
Others	4	4.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2022

The findings presented in Table 3 indicate that of the 100 respondents who participated in this study, 20% acted as DES inspectors of education standards;17% acted as Inspectors in UPE schools from the district; 21% acted as Education officers from the districts; 12% of the respondents acted as Inspectors from the Directorate Education KCCA; 11% of the respondents acted as senior Education Officersin UPE schools;9% of the respondents acted as Assistant Education officersin UPE schools; 6% of the respondents acted as chiefs in the local governments;and the remaining 4% of the respondents did not indicate their roles in the departments they worked in.

D. School Inspection Elements that Influence Quality of Education

School inspection elements include: support supervision, tools and methodology used to analyse statistical data obtained during support supervision towards improvement of quality of primary education. Before establishing the effectiveness of support supervision and association between school inspection and quality of education in primary schools, this study determined respondents’ qualification that carry out supervision; understanding of reflective indicators measured; methods of collecting evidenced data during supervision; and how the data collected are analysed. The findings regarding these are presented in the following figures and tables.

Fig 7 Showing Qualifications of Respondents who Conduct Research
Source: Primary Data, 2022

Figure 7 shows that, of the 100 participants in the study, 91% said they had the necessary qualifications to carry out teacher evaluation or supervision in elementary schools, while 9% said they lacked the qualifications to do so.

The evaluators who are external to the school are advised on certain quality indicators that are to be inspected, measured, and reported, according to MoES papers on How we inspect. The utilization of resources in the classroom, the teaching and learning process, assessment, recording, and reporting of the teacher's expertise, among other things, are also emphasized (MoES, 2012).

Table 4 Responses on Sharing Impressions of the Lesson Learnt During Supervision

During inspection/evaluation, does the observed teacher share the impressions of the lesson and meanings for their personal teaching after inspection	Frequency	Percent
Yes	45	45.0
No	55	55.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Primary data, 2022

Table 4 shows that 45% of the respondents agreed that during supervision, the observed teacher shared the impressions of the lessons and what they mean for their personal teaching after inspection, while 55% of them disagreed.

Table 5 Showing Commonly Used Methods/Tools to Collect Evidence in Supervision

What are the commonly used methods/tools to collect evidence?	Frequency	Percent
Listening to teachers	30	30.0
Reviewing records	14	14.0
Using a checklist	21	21.0
Talking with parents or students	27	27.0
Reviewing recommendations from previous visits	8	8.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2022

The question on what were the commonly used methods and tools to collect evidence during inspection was examined. The findings in Table 5 show that of the 100 respondents, 30% of them identified listening to teachers as one of the key methods used to collect evidence during supervision, 14% of them indicated reviewing previous records as one of the methods of reviewing records; 21% of the respondents indicated using checklists; 27% of the respondents pointed out talking to parents or pupils as one of the major methods of collecting evidence during supervision and 8% of the respondents indicated reviewing recommendations from previous visits as one of the key methods/tools commonly used in collecting evidence during school supervision.

Fig 8 Showing Commonly Used Methods to Analyse Evidence Collected Data on Indicators
Source: Primary Data, 2022

Respondents were asked to point out the methods that were commonly used to analyse evidence collected on indicators. Figure 8 indicates that 49% of the respondents pointed out both qualitative and quantitative methods as commonly used methods to analyse evidence collected during supervision; 31% of the respondents indicated that the evidence collected during supervision is analysed quantitatively; while 20% of the respondents cited qualitative approach being used to analyse evidence collected during supervision.

➤ *Effectiveness of support supervision during school inspection in Primary Schools*

Before establishing the association between support supervision and quality of education, this study determined the effectiveness of support supervision using mean values and standard deviations. Effectiveness in support supervision was examined in areas of independence of school inspectors; relevance of methods/tools used in supervision; teachers’ contribution during supervision; approaches of working out competence areas derived from self-assessment tools of teachers; quality teacher indicators and learning outcomes; and the importance of inspector’s professional judgement. A bare minimum mean value of 1 and a maximum mean value of 4 were used to help interpret the data. According to mean ranges from 1.00 to 1.75, the majority of respondents strongly disagreed with the items relating to school supervision in primary schools. As a result, school supervision procedures in elementary schools are very ineffectual. Mean ranges between 1.76 and 2.50 indicate that most respondents disapproved of the topics covered by the investigation of school supervision in primary schools. The majority of respondents agreed with the items examined on school supervision in primary schools; mean ranges from 2.51 to 3.25 show that school supervision techniques in primary schools are ineffective. As a result, primary school practices for school supervision are extremely effective. The mean, which runs from 3.26 to 4.00, shows that respondents strongly agreed with the questions on primary school practices for school supervision.

However, MoES data base on the teachers’ teaching practices only provides data focused on teacher pupil ratio, literacy and mathematics skills etc. and rarely presents data on teachers’ reflections on actual teaching and self-assessments based on basic minimum standards(TISSA,2013).The findings regarding these are presented in Table 6

Table 6 Mean Ranges Showing Effectiveness of Supportsupervision

Inspection Elements	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation
Through a probe of the efficacy and norms of instruction and learning, a school inspection provides an independent and external review of the level of education being given in schools.	100	1	4	3.25	.69	Effective
School’s inspection methodology and tools measure the performance indicators, quality indicators and perception measures and standards the professional code of conduct and the competences assessed stipulated in the profile for primary teachers	100	1	4	3.17	.68	Effective
The educators seek for ongoing professional development, broadening perception, self-reflection, documentation, and sharing of personal reflection.	100	1	4	2.60	.91	Effective
The self-assessment tool of primary teachers is arranged according to specific competences where the teacher obtains a score calculated as the average of the percentile scores for each competency area divided by the total number of competencies.	100	1	4	2.26	.81	Ineffective
The nature of the tools used to obtain quality teacher indicators and learning outcomes influence the policy decision on the development of other policy interventions and measures	100	1	4	2.19	.89	Ineffective
The inspector’s professional judgement is very important in the assessment and provision of the evidenced data observed on teacher’s ability to reflect	100	1	4	2.10	.86	Ineffective
Mean Average				2.59	.81	Effective

Source: Primary Data, 2022

It can be seen from the results shown in Table 6 that respondents generally regarded support supervision in primary schools as effective at the average mean value of 2.59, which corresponds to effectiveness in the rating scale at a comparatively low standard deviation of 0.81.

Table 7 Association between School Inspection and Quality Education

School Inspection Elements	N	χ^2	p-value
Qualification of Supervisors			
Yes	91 (91.0)		
No	09 (09.0)	4.34	0.000
Commonly used methods/tools to collect evidence			
Listening to teachers	30 (30.0)	3.11	0.051
Reviewing records	14 (10.0)	1.03	0.121
Using a checklist	21 (21.0)	3.21	0.041
Talking with parents or students	27 (27.0)	4.34	0.000
Reviewing recommendations from previous visits	08 (08.0)	2.33	0.120
Methods of Analyzing Evidence			
Quantitative	30 (30.0)	6.57	0.23
Qualitative	14 (10.0)		
Both Qualitative and Quantitative	21 (21.0)		
Sharing Impressions of the Lesson Learnt During Supervision			
Agreed	45(45.0)	4.04	0.021
Disagreed	55(55.0)		
School inspection give a fair and impartial assessment of the educational system's quality.			
Agreed	90(90.0)	3.18	0.020
Disagreed	10(10.0)		
School’s inspection methodology and tools measure the performance indicators, quality indicators and perception measures and standards the professional code of conduct and the competences assessed stipulated in the profile for primary teachers			
Agreed	90(90.0)	1.69	0.031
Disagreed	10(10.0)		
The teachers continuously improve your skills, broaden your perspective, evaluate your performance, and record and share your reflections.			
Agreed	49 (49.0)		
Disagreed	51(51.0)	4.91	0.010

<p>The self-assessment tool of primary teachers is arranged according to specific competences Agreed Disagreed</p>	<p>33 (33.0) 67 (67.0)</p>	<p>5.86</p>	<p>0.213</p>
<p>The nature of the tools used to obtain quality teacher indicators and learning outcomes influence the policy decision on the development of other policy interventions and measures. Agreed Disagreed</p>	<p>31 (31.0) 69 (69.0)</p>	<p>3.87</p>	<p>0.212</p>
<p>The inspector’s professional judgment is very important in the assessment and provision of the evidenced data observed on teacher’s ability to reflect Agreed Disagreed</p>	<p>24 (24.0) 76 (76.0)</p>	<p>3.22</p>	<p>0.043</p>

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Various elements of school inspection that influence the quality of education were investigated and identified in this study using Chi-Square at OR (95%CI) and standardized significant value of 0.05. The results of this research are shown in Table 4.6 and show a strong correlation between the quality of elementary school education and the supervisor's credentials. The $x^2 = 4.34$; $p = 0.00$ at the standardized significance level of 0.05 supports this conclusion.

According to the findings in Table 7, talking with parents or students, using a checklist, and listening to teachers are all positively related to educational quality. These findings were supported by $x^2 = 3.11$; $p = 0.051$ for listening to teachers, $x^2 = 3.21$; $p = 0.041$ for using a checklist, and $x^2 = 4.34$; $p = 0.000$ for all three at the standardized significant level of 0.05.

This study found out that there was a significant correlation between sharing impressions of the lesson learnt during supervision and the quality of education. This finding is shown in the $x^2 = 4.04$; $p = 0.021$ at the standardized significant level of 0.05.

The findings in Table 7 also indicate that independent and external evaluation in school inspection is significantly related to the quality of education in primary schools supported by the $x^2 = 3.18$; $p = 0.020$ at the standardized significant level of 0.05.

The findings in Table 7 also show that when quality indicators, a professional code of conduct, and the abilities specified in the profile for primary teachers are assessed during the school's inspection methodology and tools, the educational quality of primary schools can increase. The $x^2 = 1.69$; $p = 0.031$ at the standardized significant level of 0.05 indicates this finding.

In observing teachers’ practice, teacher’s plans and records are to be supervised to check whether they build on the assessment of the learners for quality improvements (MoES, 2012)

This study also shows that when teachers work to advance their professional development, broaden their perspectives, evaluate their own performance, document, and share personal reflection, the quality of education will rise. The $x^2 = 4.91$; $p = 0.010$ at the standardized significant level of 0.05 supports this finding.

Also, the teachers were still found to not be fully satisfactory in proficient teaching and hence low level of teacher performance and poor teacher competences (Brookfield, 2004; Reagan et al., 2000).

Last but not least, findings in Table 7 show that the standard of instruction in primary schools and inspectors' professional judgement are positively correlated. The $x^2 = 3.22$; $p = 0.043$ at the standardized significant level of 0.05 illustrates this fact.

As their p -values are higher than the standardized significant level of 0.05, the findings in Table 7 suggest that the following features of supervision did not significantly correlate with the quality of education in elementary schools. These include methods of analysing evidence ($x^2 = 6.57$; $p = 0.23$); the self-assessment tool of primary teachers being arranged according to specific competences ($x^2 = 5.86$; $p = 0.213$); and the nature of the tools used to obtain quality teacher indicators and learning outcomes influence the policy decision on the development of other policy interventions and measures ($x^2 = 3.87$; $p = 0.212$).

The document reviewed indicated that the supervision tools must clearly provide specific evidenced data on teacher standards focused on the teachers’ profession reflection during school performance reviews (DES, 2005; MoES, 2012).

In order to carry out their supervision effectively, inspectors use tools and methodologies which enable them to work at consistently high standards across the country (MoES, 2012).

Findings in Table 7, however, suggested that there was no significant association between evidence analysis techniques, primary teachers' self-assessment tools, and the calibre of instruction provided in primary schools ($\chi^2=6.57$; $p=0.23$). This could imply that the lack of data on instructors' self-evaluations of their own performance on shared experiences and documentation may also be due to the use of antiquated or inadequate instruments to gather the verified information on teacher standards. Collecting data is NOT all that inspection is. Anyone can gather data as long as they do so diligently and accurately. Data only raises questions that need to be asked, not the answers. The Inspectors' conduct is not included in the methodology and yet they are required to be transparent, publicly available and share with school staff (MoES, 2010).

E. Stakeholders' Responsibilities and the Quality of Education

This study used mean values and standard deviations to determine the level of supervisors' obligations before looking at the relationship between stakeholders' responsibilities and educational quality. The minimum and maximum mean values were employed to aid in the interpretation of the data; they were 1 and 4, respectively. Therefore, the majority of respondents strongly disagreed with the items researched on supervisors' responsibilities in primary schools, as indicated by mean ranges from 1.00 to 1.75. As a result, there are very few supervisory obligations in primary schools. Mean ranges between 1.76 and 2.50 indicate that most respondents disapproved of the topics covered by the investigation of supervisory responsibilities in primary schools. Consequently, basic schools have modest levels of supervisory responsibility. The majority of respondents agreed with the issues pertaining to primary school supervisors' duties, as indicated by mean ranges from 2.51 to 3.25. As a result, the level of supervisory obligations in primary schools is high. Mean responses, which range from 3.26 to 4.00, show that respondents strongly agreed with the topics covered in the investigation of supervisory responsibilities in primary schools. In primary schools, the level of supervisory responsibility is relatively high. Table 8 provides a summary of the conclusions in this regard.

Table 8 Mean Ranges Showing the Level of Supervisors' Responsibilities

Level of Supervisors' Responsibilities	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation
Senior Education officers address issues of quality teaching, and internalize and implement guidelines and policies, circulars issued by the Ministry of Education and Sports and as disseminated and explained by the District Education Office	100	1	4	2.64	.73	High
There are collective efforts in the assessment and collection of evidenced data on the primary teacher competences as standard measures of quality teaching	100	1	4	2.38	.84	Low
The findings at the school level on specific teacher competences are communicated clearly, accurately and reported on time both orally and in written summary report to the district or region, and DES to inform policy decisions on the measure of teaching	100	1	4	2.20	.85	Low
Shared responsibilities of Stakeholders in the Implementation of Universal Primary Education (UPE) for Districts and Urban Councils establish, provide and maintain quality education	100	1	4	2.06	.89	Low
School inspections reports are discussed with staff, then corrective actions for interventions are subsequently followed up by MoES	100	1	4	2.00	.84	Low
Mean average				2.26	.83	Low

Source: Primary data, 2022

The majority of respondents, as shown by the results in Table 4.7, assessed the degree of supervisors' responsibilities as low, and this conclusion is supported by the overall mean average of 2.26, which, with a standard deviation of .83, corresponds to low on the rating scale.

The achievement of standards is collated across a school, district or country, and the results expressed in percentages focus on pupil teacher ratio, teacher attendancenot on the overall supersion on teaching practice (MoES,2019).

The level of supervisors' responsibilities was rated low. The majority of respondents disagreed that there were collective efforts in the assessment and collection of evidenced data on the primary teacher competences as standard measures of quality teaching (mean=2.38; std.dev=.84). They also disagreed that the findings at the school level on specific teacher competences were communicated clearly, accurately and reported on time both orally and in written summary report to the district or region, and DES to inform policy decisions on the measure of teaching (mean=2.20; std.dev=.85). They further disagreed that shared responsibilities of Stakeholders in the Implementation of Universal Primary Education (UPE) for Districts and Urban Councils establish, provide and maintain quality education (mean=2.06; std.dev=.89). Finally, respondents disagreed that school inspections reports are discussed with staff, then corrective actions for interventions are subsequently followed up by MoES (mean=2.00; std.dev=.84).

A high rating was given to one aspect of supervisors' duties, but the majority of respondents agreed that Senior Education Officers address issues of quality teaching, internalize and implement guidelines and policies, circulars issued by the Ministry of Education and Sports, and as disseminated and explained by the District Education Office. Therefore, the ability of the senior education officer or head teacher to mentor and support the teacher would have a significant impact on the achievement of the quality of learning at the school level.

The DES's guides should be used by a variety of people, including school staff, governing body members, local government officials in charge of quality control, Ministry officials, including national inspectors who collaborate with DES (Part 1: How can we improve our school, 2012).

Table 9 Association between Supervisor’s Responsibilities and Quality of Education

Supervisors’ Responsibilities	N	χ^2	p-value
Addressing quality of teaching, and internalize and implement guidelines and policies, circulars issued by the Ministry of Education and Sports and as disseminated and explained by the District Education Office Agreed Disagreed	32(32.0) 68(68.0)	5.12	0.000
There are collective efforts in the assessment and collection of evidenced data on the primary teacher competences as standard measures of quality teaching Agreed Disagreed	22(22.0) 78(78.0)	2.08	0.001
The findings at the school level on specific teacher competences are communicated clearly, accurately and reported on time both orally and in written summary report to the district or region, and DES to inform policy decisions on the measure of teaching Agreed Disagreed	61(61.0) 39(39.0)	4.63	0.012
Shared Stakeholders' Responsibilities for Districts and Urban Councils in the Implementation of Universal Primary Education (UPE) establish, provide and maintain quality education Agreed Disagreed	67(67.0) 33(33.0)	2.90	0.041
School inspections reports are discussed with staff, then corrective actions for interventions are subsequently followed up by MoES Agreed Disagreed	19(33.0) 81(81.0)	6.12	0.013

Source: Primary Data, 2022

The results in Table 4.8 demonstrate that all the variables examined in relation to supervisory responsibilities have a significant impact on the quality of teaching in primary schools. The results show that when issues of high-quality teaching are given priority, such as reflective practice, internalized and applied rules and regulations, circulars issued by the Ministry of Education and Sports, and as distributed and clarified by the District Education Office, the level of education in primary schools will rise 5.12 times. This conclusion is supported by both the $x^2 = 5.12$ and significant (p) value of 0.000 at the standardized significant level of 0.05.

The results also show that when there are group efforts in the assessment and gathering of evidence-based data on the primary teacher competences as standard measures of quality teaching, the quality of education will increase by 2.08 times. The significant (p) value of 0.001 at the standardized significant threshold of 0.05 and the $x^2 = 2.08$ support this finding.

The results in Table 4.8 also show that when the district, region, and DES receive clear, accurate, and timely oral and written summaries of the findings at the school level regarding specific teacher competences in order to inform policy decisions on the measure of teaching, the quality of education will increase by 4.63 times. $x^2 = 4.63$ and a significant (p) value of 0.012 at the standardized significant threshold of 0.05 both support this conclusion.

The shared obligations of Stakeholders in the Implementation of Universal Primary Education (UPE) for Districts and Urban Councils to establish, supply, and sustain quality education are also shown in Table 4.8, however the relationship between the two is very weak. The significant (p) value of 0.041 at the standardized significant level of 0.05 and the $x^2 = 2.90$ both support this conclusion. This implies that whenever there are shared duties of stakeholders in the implementation of universal primary education (UPE) for districts and urban councils to build, provide, and maintain quality education, the quality of education will increase 2.90 times.

Last but not least, the study reveals that any time school inspection findings are addressed with staff and corrective measures for interventions are then followed up on by MoES, education quality will improve 6.12 times. $\chi^2=6.12$ and the significant (p) value of 0.013 at the standardized significant level of 0.05 both support this conclusion.

Inspectors must also rely on evidence when making judgements among other things, teaching and learning in the classroom, instructors' perspectives: How can we enhance our school, 2012 (Part 1).

F. Mentorship Support and Quality of Primary School Education

The purpose of this study was to ascertain the respondents' perceptions of the value of mentorship as an aspect of teacher education that fosters reflective practice and the professional growth of teachers, as well as whether or not mentors during support supervision create opportunities and facilitate experiences that develop the instructor's ability for reflecting on his or her practice. The accompanying figure and tables contain summaries of the findings with reference to these.

Fig 9 Showing Whether Support supervision strengthens Professional reflection
Source: Primary data, 2022

On whether support supervision strengthens professional reflection or not, the result in Figure 4.7 indicates that of the 100 respondents, 73% agreed that support supervision strengthens professional reflection, while 27% disagreed that it does not strengthen professional reflection.

Table 10 Showing the Importance of Mentorship as part of Teacher Education that Enhances Reflective Practice and the Professional Development

Mentoring is an important part of teacher education that enhances reflective practice and the professional development of teachers	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	4	4.0
Disagree	10	10.0
Agree	55	55.0
Strongly Agree	31	31.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Primary data, 2022

Findings in Table 10 clearly demonstrate that, of the 100 respondents who took part in the study, 4% strongly disagreed that mentoring is a crucial component of teacher education that improves reflective practice and school professional development, 10% disagreed, and 55% agreed.

Table 11 Whether Supervisors or Mentors Provide Experiences and Opportunities During Support Supervision that Help Teachers Build their Capacity to Reflect on their Practice.

During Support supervision the supervisor (mentors) the ability of teachers to ponder on their work should be developed; provide chances and promote experiences in this regard.	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	6	6.0
Disagree	8	8.0
Agree	62	62.0
Strongly Agree	24	24.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Primary data, 2022

Additionally, findings in Table 4.10 reveal that, of the 100 participants in this study, 6% strongly disagreed that the supervisor (mentors) create opportunities and facilitate experiences that develop the teacher's capacity to reflect on his or her practice, and 8% disagreed that the head teacher or mentor create opportunities and facilitate experiences that develop the teacher's capacity to reflect. 62% of respondents were in agreement that during support supervision, the mentors and supervisors create chances and facilitate experiences that help teachers improve their capacity for self-reflection; and 24% firmly agreed that the head teacher or supervisor (mentors) should create chances and arrange experiences to help teachers develop their capacity to reflect on their practice.

Table 12 Demonstrating how Excellent Mentors Serve as Positive Role Models by Engaging in Exemplary Professional Conduct

On a scale of 1 to 5 where 1 is the least effective and 5 is the most effective, how effective do you provide a positive role model through demonstration of exemplary professional behaviours?	Frequency	Percent
5	16	16.0
4	29	29.0
3	55	55.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Findings in Table 12 show that out of the 100 respondents who took part in the study, none rated themselves as very ineffective and ineffective at serving as a positive role model by exemplifying exemplary professional behaviours; 16% rated themselves highly effective; and 29% rated themselves as very effective or effective at doing so.

Table 13 Showing Frequency on Questions on Reflective Indicators are Brought Up During Inspection Routines

How often are questions on reflective indicators brought up during inspection routines? Please select all that apply	Frequency	Percent
Always	9	9.0
Once every inspection	20	20.0
Not sure what this is	45	45.0
I have never heard or been asked questions regarding reflective indicators	26	26.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2022

On how often are questions on reflective indicators brought up during inspection routines, the results in Table 13 indicate that 9% of the 100 respondents who participated in this study indicated that they always question on reflective indicators during inspection routines; 20% stated that they question on reflective indicators during inspection routines once every inspection; 45% were not sure; and 26% had never heard or been asked questions regarding reflective indicators.

One of the examples given to inspectors on how they can contribute to the improvement in schools was to interact with head teachers, promoted school staff, class teachers, learners and members of the community. They were encouraged to ask them questions which encourage them to think deeply about their own practice and the quality of education provided by the school (MoES, 2012).

Table 14 Showing Ways of Engaging in Self-Reflection after Observing a Teacher

After observing a teacher how do you both engage in self-reflection? Please select all that apply	Frequency	Percent
The inspector reflects on the lesson and formulates possible questions on post lessons	36	36.0
The inspector reviews the notes of the observed teacher and draws conclusions	32	32.0
Both	32	32.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Findings in Table 14 findings provide information on how the mentor and teacher engage in self-reflection. Of the 100 respondents who took part in this study, 36% said they both do so by formulating questions after lessons and reflecting on the lesson; 32% said they do so by observing teacher reviews of the notes and drawing conclusions; and 32% said they both engaged using the two aforementioned methods.

Also, the inspectors look at the teachers' plans and records (DES, 2005; MoES,2012).

Table 15 Mentorship Support and Quality of Primary School Education

Teacher's Responsibilities	N	χ^2	p-value
Whether Support supervision strengthens Professional reflection or not Agreed Disagreed	47(47.0) 53(53.0)	3.14	0.000
Importance of mentorship as part of teacher education that enhances reflective practice and the professional development of schools Agreed Disagreed	86(86.0) 14(14.0)	2.19	0.032
Whether during support supervision mentors create opportunities and facilitate experiences that develop teacher's capacity to reflect on their practice or not Agreed Disagreed	40(22.0) 07(78.0)	3.08	0.010
Level of effectiveness among education stakeholders in providing a positive role model through demonstration of exemplary professional behaviors 5 4 3	16(16.0) 29(29.0) 55(55.0)	5.03	0.001
Frequency on questions on reflective indicators brought up during inspection routines Always Once every inspection Not sure what this is Never heard or been asked questions regarding reflective indicators	09 (09.0) 20(20.0) 45(45.0) 26(26.0)	5.02	0.160
How both the mentor and the teacher engage in self-reflection Inspector reflects about the lesson and formulates possible questions for post lessons The inspector observes notes on teacher reviews and draws conclusions Both	64(64.0) 28(28.0) 08(08.0)	3.28	0.201

Source: Primary Data, 2022

The information in Table 15 shows that there is a connection between the standard of instruction in primary schools and the many facets of mentoring as well as a deepening of professional reflection among support supervision. This conclusion is supported by both the $x^2=3.14$ and significant (p) value of 0.000 at the standardized significant level of 0.05.

The findings in Table 15 further demonstrate that when mentorship is considered a crucial component of teacher education that improves reflective practice and the professional growth of schools, the quality of education in primary schools will increase 2.19 times. The significant (p) value of 0.032 at the standardized significant threshold of 0.05 and the $x^2 = 2.19$ support this finding.

Additionally, Table 15's data demonstrate that when mentors provide chances and promote experiences that strengthen teachers' capacity to reflect on their practice during support supervision, the quality of education will increase by 3.08 times. The $x^2 = 3.08$ and significant (p) value of 0.010 at the standardized significant threshold of 0.05 serve as evidence for this conclusion.

Furthermore, Table 15's findings demonstrate that when education stakeholders are successful in serving as a positive role model by exhibiting admirable professional behavior, the quality of education will increase by a factor of 5.03 times. The significant (p) value of 0.001 at the standardized significant threshold of 0.05 and the $x^2 = 5.03$ both support this conclusion.

However, because the p-values of the two items in this study were greater than 0.05 (the standardized significant value), there was no significant relationship between the frequency of questions on reflective indicators brought up during inspection routines and the way the mentor and the teacher engage in self-reflection.

The supervisors tend to focus more on the learner's perspective instead of the teacher's perspectives while observing classroom practice and out of class activities(MoES,2012).

G. School Performance Reviews and Quality of Primary School Education

One of the recommendations for institutional self-evaluation as a tactic to enhance performance in teacher education institutions is the use of school performance reviews (MoES, 2012 & DES, 2005).

The final study goal demonstrated a link between school performance evaluation and primary school educational quality. The most popular methods used by primary school teachers to reflect on their teaching, the respondents' knowledge of reflective practices, and the respondents' views on the significance of school evaluation in guiding the process of data collection on school and the effectiveness of professional reflection of primary teachers were all determined in this study before the relationship between the two variables was established. Concerns about the quality of the implementation of the indicators of reflective practice, the respondents' opinions on the evidence of reflective practice in teaching, their opinion on whether support supervision strengthens professional reflection, and their opinion on whether the ethos and indicators of reflective practice are enforced. The tables and figure below present the results in relation to these.

Table 16 Showing Respondents' Understanding Regarding Reflective Indicators (Based on Multiple Responses)

What is considered as reflective indicators within the evaluation tool as per the primary teacher competency profile?	Frequency	Percent
Change in behaviour	4	2.2
Teacher self-evaluation	16	8.8
Performance evaluation	17	9.4
Primary teacher needs	6	3.3
Teachers relevance	23	12.7
Content, pedagogy and personality	6	3.3
Leadership style	13	7.2
Teaching methods and assessment	12	6.6
Lesson plans, schemes of work, record of work, content coverage	9	5.0
Duty roster, record keeping, marking learners' books	5	2.8
Performance targets	4	2.2
Communication skills	7	3.9
Creativity	4	2.2
Presentation of content	12	6.6
Key performance indicators	7	3.9
Staff appraisal	6	3.3
Teacher-pupil interactions	4	2.2
Teacher to teacher sharing	6	3.3
Not sure	20	11.0
Total	181	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Table 16 shows that respondents had various levels of understanding regarding reflective indicators. Using multiple responses of 181, 2.2% of the respondents believe reflective indicator relates to change in behaviour; 8.8% understand the term as teacher self-evaluation; 9.4% understand the term as performance evaluation; 3.3% understand reflective indicators as primary teacher needs; 12.7% understand reflective indicators as teacher's relevance; 3.3% cited reflective indicators as content, pedagogy and personality; 7.2% related it to leadership style; for 6.6%, reflective indicators as teaching methods and assessment; 5% believed it is lesson plans, schemes of work, record of work, content coverage; 2.8 viewed the term as duty roster, record keeping, marking learners' books; for 2.2% , it was performance targets; 3.9% related the term with communication skills; 2.2% believed that reflective indicator was same as creativity; 6.6% thought that reflective indicators are presentation of contents; 3.9% saw it as key performance indicators; 3.3% reflective indicators related to staff appraisal; for 2.2%, reflective indicators were teacher-pupil interactions; 3.3% saw it as teacher to teacher sharing; and up to 11% were not sure about what the term meant.

Using multiple responses of 181, 11% were not sure about what reflective indicators meant. In the document 'How can we improve the school'(2012), SPR is a supported self-evaluation technique that is done annually by a team from the school in collaboration with the regional inspector, AA, and CCT. It is claimed to be a useful method for determining what needs to be improved upon and the course of action that has to be taken. It offers guidelines on what to assess in the school inspectors' handbook. The SPR teams are also given instructions on what to analyse, including crucial data, attendance and assessment records, lesson plans, etc. Through the method of ongoing evaluation for enhancement of quality in primary education, they determine if assessment is integrated with learning and instruction.

Table 17 Showing Whether School Evaluation is very Important in Guiding the Process of Data Collection on School and Effectiveness of Professional Reflection of the Primary Teachers or Not

School evaluation is very important in guiding the process of data collection on school and effectiveness of professional reflection of the primary teachers.	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	7	7.0
Disagree	9	9.0
Agree	69	69.0
Strongly Agree	15	15.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2022

The findings presented in Table 4.16 indicate that of the 100 people who participated in this study, 7% strongly disagreed that School Evaluation was very important in guiding the process of data collection on school and effectiveness of professional reflection of the primary teachers; 9% disagreed that School Evaluation was very important in guiding the process of data collection on school and effectiveness of professional reflection of the primary teachers; 69% agreed that School Evaluation was very important in guiding the process of data collection on school and effectiveness of professional reflection of the primary teachers; and 15% strongly agreed that School Evaluation was very important in guiding the process of data collection on school and effectiveness of professional reflection of the primary teachers.

According to Ministry of Education and sports guide Part 1; 'How can we improve our school' (2012), the needs and entitlements of young people are always a priority just as the professional conduct of teachers to meet their highest standards for quality learner outcomes.

Table 18 Indicating the Most Common Practices used by Primary School Teachers to Reflect on their Teaching (Based on Multiple Responses)

As a stakeholder, what are the most common practices used by primary school teachers to reflect on their teaching?	Frequency	Percent
Explaining concepts to Students	9	6.9
interpret questions and concepts where need is identified	26	20.0
Support students to apply concepts and knowledge	27	20.8
Encourage students to have varying perspectives	21	16.2
Empathize with learners	40	30.8
All the above	7	5.4
Total	130	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2022

This study also looked into the typical methods primary school instructors use to reflect on their instruction. According to the findings in Table 18, of the 130 responses, 6.9% said that explaining concepts to students was the most frequent practice primary school teachers used to reflect on their instruction; 20% said that interpreting questions and concepts when a need was identified was the most frequent practice; 20.8% noted that helping students apply concepts and knowledge was the most frequent method used by primary school teachers to reflect on their teaching; 16.2% said that promoting students' diversity of viewpoints was the most frequent method used by primary school teachers to reflect on their teaching; 30.8% said that empathizing with students was the most frequent method used by primary school teachers to reflect on their teaching; and 5.4% said that all the above were the most common practices used by primary school teachers to reflect on their teaching.

Table 19 Showing the Level of Knowledge about Reflective Practice among the Participants in the Study

On a scale of 1-5 with 5 being the highest, how much do you know about reflective practice?	Frequency	Percent
I have heard about reflective practice but don't know much about it	25	25.0
I know what reflective practice is and try my best to learn more about it	10	10.0
I know and practice reflective practice in my teaching	6	6.0
I don't know what reflective practice is and never heard of it	59	59.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2022

This study determined the level of knowledge among different education stakeholders about the reflective practice. The findings in Table 4.18 clearly show that of the 100 respondents who participate in this study, 25% noted that they had heard about reflective practice but did not know much about it; 10% stated that they knew what reflective practice was and tried their best to learn more about it; 6% noted that they knew and practiced reflective practice in their teaching; and 59% clearly noted that they did not know what reflective practice was and had never heard of it.

Fig 10 Showing whether Ethos and Indicators of Reflective Practice are Enforced or Not
Source: Primary Data, 2022

On whether ethos and indicators of reflective practice are enforced or not, the findings in Figure 4.8 shows that 76% of the respondents disagreed that the ethos and indicators of reflective practice were not being enforced at schools while 24% of them agreed that the ethos and indicators of reflective practice were being enforced at schools.

Table 20 Showing the Level of Concern about the Quality of Implementation of Reflective Practice

What are the concerns about the quality of its implementation?	Frequency	Percent
Low: No/small likelihood of being enacted	64	64.0
Medium: Moderate likelihood of being enacted	28	28.0
High: High likelihood of being enacted	8	8.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2022

The findings in Table 4.19 show that of the 100 respondents who participated in this study, 64% rated the level of concern about the quality of implementation of reflective practice low (No/small likelihood of being enacted); 28% rated the level of concerns about the quality of implementation of reflective practice medium (moderate likelihood of being enacted), and 8% rated the level of concern about the quality of implementation of reflective practice high (high likelihood of being enacted).

The Level of concern about the quality of implementation of reflective practice has a high likelihood of being enacted. There are quality indicators in the Handbook for School Inspectors and how they are used by the school staff to help them identify strengths and areas of improvement using guides in series How can we improve our school?(MoES,2012)

Table 21 Showing Evidence of Reflective Practice in Teaching in UPE Schools

What is the evidence of reflective practice in a teaching?	Frequency	Percent
Maintaining professional standards	19	19.0
Documentation and shared personal reflection	40	40.0
Indicators on continuous professional development	21	21.0
All the above	8	8.0
Not certain	12	12.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2022

This study unearthed the evidence of reflective practice in teaching in UPE schools. The findings presented in Table 4.20 indicate that of the 100 participants of this study, 19% indicated maintaining professional standards as evidence of reflective practice in teaching in UPE schools; 40% indicated documentation and shared personal reflection as evidence of reflective practice in teaching in UPE schools; 21% indicated indicators on continuous professional development as evidence of reflective practice in teaching in UPE schools; 8% stated all of the above as evidence of reflective practice in teaching in UPE schools; and 12% of the respondents were not certain about the evidences of reflective practice in teaching.

Of the 100 participants, only 40% indicated documentation and shared personal reflection as evidence of reflective practice in teaching in UPE schools. Evidence of reflective practice in teaching includes Qis developed by DES to help inspectors make judgements about the quality of education in individual schools for example, supervision of teaching and learning, teachers' planning, teaching and learning process among others(MoES,2012).

Table 22 School Performance Review and Quality of Primary School Education

Teacher's Responsibilities	N	χ^2	p-value
Respondents' Understanding Regarding Reflective Indicators			
Low	67(66.0)	4.11	0.010
High	33(33.0)		
School evaluation in guiding the process of data collection on school and effectiveness of professional reflection of the primary teachers is important			
Agreed	84(84.0)	3.01	0.002
Disagreed	16(16.0)		
Common practices used by primary school teachers to reflect on their teaching			
Explaining concepts to Students	09(61.0)	6.09	0.161
Interpret questions and concepts where need is identified	26(39.0)	2.10	0.021
Support students to apply concepts and knowledge	27(22.0)	2.18	0.040
Encourage students to have varying perspectives	21(78.0)	1.02	0.060
Empathize with learners	40(22.0)	3.08	0.020
All the above	07(78.0)	5.05	0.010
Level of Knowledge about reflective practice among Participants in this Study			
No knowledge	67(67.0)	4.10	0.001
Low knowledge	33(33.0)		
High knowledge and practice	33(33.0)		
Whether there is an Enforcement of ethos and indicators of reflective practice in primary schools or not			
Agreed	24 (24.0)	5.02	0.000
Disagreed	76 (76.0)		
Level of concerns about the quality of implementation of reflective practice			
Low	64(64.0)	3.28	0.001
Medium	28(28.0)		
High	08(08.0)		

Source: Primary Data, 2022

According to the findings in Table 21, some school performance review items are strongly correlated with the standard of instruction in primary schools, but other things are not correlated with it at all. Although the majority of respondents do not have a thorough comprehension of reflective indicators, as can be seen from the table, a sufficient understanding of reflective indicators across various education stakeholders is related to the quality of education. This shows that when stakeholders are aware of reflective indicators, the quality of education in elementary schools will increase 4.11 times. The $x^2 = 4.11$ and significant (p) value of 0.010 at the standardized significant threshold of 0.05 both support this conclusion.

Table 22 also indicates that the quality of education will improve 3.01 times when school evaluation in guiding the process of data collection on school and effectiveness of professional reflection of the primary teachers is importantly considered. This result is supported by the $x^2 = 3.01$ and the significant (p) value of 0.002 at the standardized significant level of 0.05.

Some of the common practices used by primary school teachers to reflect on their teaching were associated with the quality of education in primary schools and these include: interpreting questions and concepts where need is identified ($x^2 = 2.10$; p-value=0.021); support students to apply concepts and knowledge ($x^2 = 2.18$; p-value=0.040); enhancing emphasis with learners ($x^2 = 3.08$; p-value=0.020); and using all the above practices ($x^2 = 5.05$; p-value=0.010) at the standardized significant level of 0.05. However, explaining concepts to students; and encouraging students to have varying perspectives as common practices individually did not have any significant association with the quality of education in primary schools and this finding was justified by the overall significant values which were greater than the standardized significant value of 0.05.

The findings in Table 4.21 indicate that the quality of education is associated with the level of knowledge about reflective practice among education stakeholders. Thus, the quality of education will improve 4.10 times with every increase in the level of knowledge about reflective practice among education stakeholders. This finding is supported by the $x^2 = 4.10$ and the significant (p) value of 0.001 at the standardized significant level of 0.05.

Furthermore, the results presented in Table 4.21 demonstrate that the quality of education will improve 5.02 times with every level of enforcement of ethos and indicators of reflective practice in primary schools. This finding is supported by the $x^2 = 5.02$ and the significant (p) value of 0.000 at the standardized significant level of 0.05.

Finally, the findings in Table 4.21 show that the quality of education in primary schools will improve 3.28 times with every increase in the level of concerns about the quality of implementation of reflective practice. This study is justified by the $x^2 = 3.28$ and the significant (p) value of 0.001 at the standardized significant level of 0.05.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

A. Introduction

The results in chapter five are discussed based on the findings in chapter four and the discussion of the results is aligned with the four (4) research objectives.

The research findings discussed clearly bring out the contributions of school Inspection toward improving the quality of primary school education. Findings provide information on the stakeholders' shared responsibilities toward improving the quality of primary education in Uganda. These can translate into implementation strategies that provide an enabling environment for successful interventions of support supervision. Furthermore, findings also provide relevant information on whether in providing mentorship support to teachers the best strategy is to strengthen professional reflection to support teachers to realize competences in their teaching. Conclusively, the findings summarize literature on the existing information on the significance of the School Performance Review reports and highlight the gaps that would need the attention of policy implementers to come up with appropriate intervention measures on the evaluation of specific teachers' standards of professional reflection.

B. Effectiveness of Support Supervision towards the Improvement of Quality Education in Uganda

According to the DES (2012) on how well is our school led serie, support supervision as an activity, supervisors are given groups of questions to ask and discuss them with their staff(QI 11 and QI 10) on support supervision and among which are reflective questions on performance appraisal, results on agreed targets for support and improvement, outcomes of support supervision as well as self-assessment by the teachers. The the quality of education will certainly improve when teachers strive for continuous professional development; widen their perception; reflect on personal performance; document and share personal reflection and given adequate support supervision. At the standardized significant level of 0.05 where $\chi^2=4.91$; $p=0.010$ as confirmed, the finding suggests that the quality of education in primary schools will improve 4.91 times when teachers strive for continuous professional development; widen their perception; reflect on personal performance; document and share personal reflection.

Also, in the documents reviewed such as Part 1:How well are we led?; How can we improve our school, and Part 6: How inspect (MoES,2010 and 2012) by DES and MoES provide quality indicators (QI) and guides on how inspection can improve quality education through effective use of supervision tools and methods.It is also stated that support supervision would be regarded invalid if the findings were not communicated clearly, accurately and on time especially to head teachers, staff and other stakeholders as both an oral report and a written summary report, to help them improve their school.The nature of the tools used to obtain quality teacher indicators and learning outcomes influence the policy decision on the development of other policy interventions (World Bank, 2006) and the Inspectors' professional code of conduct is so significant in the methodology (MoES,2010).

However, on rating elements that make support supervision effective, the methods and methodology for support supervision did not show any significant association with quality of education in primary school supervision according to findings in Table 4.6. The results in the aspects under supervisionsuch as methods of analysing evidence, the self-assessment tool of primary teachers being arranged according to specific competences and the nature of the tools used to obtain quality teacher indicators did not have any significant association with quality of education in primary school supervision.

Hence, it is unlikely that mixed methods employed to collect data are limited to analysing these indicators prioritized to improve quality education. Data on Quality Education indicators reflects more on the learning outcomes rather than the quality inputs of the teachers that contribute to Quality Education (Uganda Education Statistical Abstract, 2009).The challenge in this is that the quality indicators in the inspectors' Handbook does not have detailed and yet specific indicators for which supervision tools can be used to collect data on the nature of documentary evidence and teacher's perceptions based on reflective questions asked and experiences to influence action for quality improvement on teaching. For instance, support supervisors tend to recall Quality Indicators related to the quality of teaching by evaluating the learners' attainment in class work and examinations. This is why there is more evidenced statistical data on learning outcomes compared to teachers' perceptions, experiences and any other documentary evidence on their self-evaluation that improve quality education.

The mismatch in the measurement of learner outcomes and assessment on quality teaching has further widened the gaps in teaching practices.

And there are questions that supervisors have failed to answer due to mismatch in the measure of specific indicators. For example: If learners' attainment is poor, how then can teaching and learning processes be evaluated as good?

Hence there are inconsistencies in the tool used and lack of specific tools for measuring and analysing supervision of teaching which is a hinderance to influencing policy improvements on quality of primary education(DES,2012).

It is for this reason that some researchers such as De Grauwe (2001&2007), Diarra et al. (1997), Garforth (2004), Gumbi and Dlamini (1997), Lugaz et al. (2006), Solaux (1997) who conducted researched on school supervision in Africa reported in their findings that there is lack of satisfaction among teachers and supervisors on the impact of supervision on the classroom.

For quality improvements, reflective supervisors (DES,2012) on 'How well our school led', skilled facilitators are critical towards quality improvements in education. As skilled facilitators during the inspection, they choose, combine, add to and edit the questions so that they cover the areas of focus for the inspection. Without the knowledge on the assessment area and question design and techniques on asking questions, it would be difficult to facilitate the supervision conference and getting the needed feedback on teachers' views, experiences and documentary evidence on self-assessment by the teacher. Osterman and Kottkamp et al. (1993) highlighted the importance of a skilled facilitator who is a teacher and who shares experiences usually drawn from reflective practice.

Additionally, there is a positive correlation between inspectors' professional judgement and the quality of education as confirmed by the $\chi^2=3.22$; $p=0.043$ at the standardized significant level of 0.05. This finding implies that the quality of education will improve 3.22 times when inspectors consider sticking to their professional judgement. According to Part 6 on 'How we Inspect' guide (MoES, 2012), the stakeholders such as the DES Inspectors are required to provide accurate, comprehensive and reliable information, intelligence and data about the quality of education in individual schools and across the country. Therefore this professional judgement on supervision of teachers needs to be accurately, comprehensively quantified or described and documented as reliable feedback to inform the researchers and policy makers for quality improvements in education.

However, without the guides to both the teachers and supervisors provided in the document on Evaluating and improving quality education(2012), there would be a disastrous impact on the outcomes of supervision. So supervisors should not merely visit teachers in their classrooms to find out whether they are present or absent, or to observe if learners are happy or not or being there to show them that they care more about what happens in the classroom and motivating them to be around, but rather to share impressions of the lesson learnt and experiences during supervision. The findings reflected a significant correlation between sharing impressions of the lesson learnt during support supervision and the quality of education. At the standardized significant level of 0.05, the quality of education in primary schools will improve by 4.04 times where the $\chi^2=4.04$. This suggests that sharing impressions of the lesson learnt by the teacher as feedback to the supervisor provides a basis for the improvement of weak areas and maintenance of strong areas for quality education.

Much as supervision in primary schools was generally rated as effective, there were shortfalls especially on the nature of the tools used to obtain quality teacher indicators during supervision of teaching.

Without forgetting that the methodology of school inspection plays an important part in data collection, Bennett (1978) argued that lack of detail from school inspection methodology made it difficult to assess the reliability of the inspection evidence and findings.

C. Stakeholders' Role and Responsibilities in the Improvement of Quality Primary Education in Uganda

The Ministry of Education and Sports together with the ESA provide guidelines for stakeholders monitoring and Supporting Policy (ESA,2005) and guidelines on teacher professionalism and competences (ESA,2005). The purpose of the guides help all the involved stakeholders including the teachers to work together such as: local governments in charge of school inspections, Districts, School administrators, mentors and coaches from the Directorate etc. with an aim to promote quality of primary education and ensure that evaluation of quality measures and standards for quality of primary education are done as stipulated in the Education Sector Strategic Plan 2017/18- 2019/20 and Universal Primary Education policies respectively.

While analysing the stakeholders' role and responsibilities towards the improvement of quality primary education, Danim (2005) explains that the impact of leadership abilities on the empowerment of the teacher and improving the quality of learning processes and products is key. It is therefore the role of the supervisors who provide support supervision to the teachers to ensure that teachers are supported, advised and guided (DES, 2012).

Danim (2005) explained that the principal's (head teacher/senior education officers) leadership abilities are the major determinant of teacher empowerment and improving the quality of learning processes and products. The principal or head teacher or senior education officer is the person who is most responsible for whether teachers and school staff can work optimally.

Collective actions are pertinent for quality improvement in the education system. The stakeholders' roles according to the findings in Table 4.7, the level of supervisors' responsibilities was rated low due to a number of reasons:

- Respondents disagreed that there are collective efforts in the assessment and collection of evidenced data on the primary teacher competences as standard measures of quality teaching;
- They disagreed that the findings at the school level on specific teacher competences are communicated clearly, accurately and reported on time both orally and in written summary report to the district or region;

- They disagreed that shared responsibilities of Stakeholders in the Implementation of Universal Primary Education (UPE) for Districts and Urban Councils establish, provide and maintain quality education;
- They disagreed that school inspection reports are discussed with staff, then collective actions for interventions are subsequently followed up by MoES.

The Ministry of Education and Sports (2010) indicated gaps in the provision of collaborative support supervision and the school administrators, and at local level through the work of inspectors working within districts, sub-counties and municipalities that have led to laxity in boosting the teacher pillar for improved quality and poor performance has been registered. MoES further shows concern that a lot still needs to be done with regard to increasing equitable access to quality and relevant education and sports if the country's education system is to stay abreast with the requirements of the job market and global trends (ESSP FY 2017/18 – 2019/20).

Additionally, some of the stakeholders who provide support supervision, for example reflective leaders, ask questions and discuss with their staff and make sure that they are regularly included in the agenda of meetings by the governing body (DES, 2012) in 'How well is our school led', part 2. It is mentioned that support supervision guides help teachers to build on their strengths, develop their professional skills and grow in confidence.

However, support supervision is being affected by confusion among teams on which guides to use -- whether from MoES or DES or KYU -- especially when it comes to supervision of teaching and assessing teachers competence profile (ESA, 2005 and MoES, 2011). Some of the teacher profiles were found shelved and not put in use to influence the next step of action for quality improvement in teaching. If confusion arises among the influencers, then there is no way they can impact positive change towards improving those they offer support supervision. The participants rated the level of supervisors' responsibilities low in Table 4.7 as they disagreed that the school level on specific teacher competences are communicated clearly, accurately and reported on time both orally and in written summary report to the district or region.

This is not different from Sallis's (2011) explanation that it is the responsibility of the leader in charge to improve the quality and support all educators and education personnel to carry out the strategic steps that have been formulated by the leader. The leader in charge in this context is MoES and her counterparts who provide school inspection should communicate clearly, accurately and give feedback on time both orally and in written summary report to the district or region and other stakeholders who influence policy improvement for quality primary education.

All in all, all stakeholders should be fully aware of guides on supervision of teaching and evaluation, and tool use, be able to provide feedback on statistical data whenever support supervision is done. In as much as the senior education officers influence decision making at the school level, documentary evidence should be analysed to inform the stakeholders about the issues of teaching that would require policy interventions on how teachers can improve their work competently both individually and collectively instead of reprimanding about their absenteeism.

Also, the Government acknowledges the importance that must be attached to the quality of its teachers by recognizing the key role of leadership and service which teachers play in implementing policies and programmes (Para 382). The teachers and the stakeholders play development roles of promoting the spirit of collective responsibility of the school and the teaching profession exemplifying basic moral values and the ethics of the teaching profession and promoting the spirit of collective responsibility which educational institutions owe to the public according to chapter 8 in the Government White Paper on Education (1992) document (Ref Para 383, 384, 385).

D. Mentorship Support for the Improvement of Quality Primary Education in Uganda

According to objective 3 on the study on mentorship support and quality of primary school education, the Literature under review identified gaps in the Low levels in education quality as being affected by the teachers' inputs (BASIC EDUCATION SECTOR ANALYSIS REPORT, 2012).]

Ideally from what is written in the documents on 'How we inspect part 1', 'How well we are led', and 'How can we improve our school', the Inspectors representing the different institutions under MoES are expected to develop attitudes and behaviours that enable them to focus on bringing about improvement for the sake of the children in schools (DES, 2005 and MoES, 2010; 2012).

Through Mentorship in particular, supervisors are expected to model or practice being honest, impartial and having a sense of integrity in their practice so as to be able to develop the kinds of relationships with teachers and leaders in schools and districts to enable them become constructive and persuasive when providing feedback, while also remaining firm and focused above all on what is best for the school generally.

Of the 100 respondents, 73% of them agreed that Mentorship as an element of support supervision strengthen professional reflection. While 27% of them disagreed that it does not strengthen professional reflection, this difference in the responses can

suggest that some stakeholders are still not aware about the role of mentorship in strengthening professional reflection as an element of support supervision. The changes could be related to education differences of respondents and different levels of involvement of respondents in conducting support supervision-related practices.

Additionally, when respondents were asked on whether mentors create opportunities and facilitate experiences that develop teacher's capacity to reflect on their practice or not during supervision, 62% of the respondents agreed while 24% of the respondents strongly agreed that during support supervision the supervisors such as Senior education officers and their assistants (mentors) create opportunities and facilitate experiences that develop the teacher's capacity to reflect on his or her practice.

Flynn and Nolan(2008, pp. 173–174) indicate that best practices have been developed regarding mentoring programmes following school-based programmatic components and processes that are significant such as: i) selection of mentors with the same certification and in close proximity to their mentees, ii) providing mentors and mentees schedules that allow common planning time and opportunities to observe each other, iii) reduced workloads for mentees, and iv) providing orientations for both mentors and mentees.

Although none of the respondents rated themselves as very ineffective and ineffective in providing a positive role model through demonstration of exemplary professional behaviours, 16% of the respondents rated themselves as highly effective. The impression from this is that efforts should be put in place to ensure that different education stakeholders are effectively involved in providing a positive role model through demonstration of exemplary professional behaviours as guided in the Handbook for supervisors that inspectors' professional conduct meets the highest standards with the four key values such as Integrity, Honesty, Objectivity and Impartiality that lie behind inspectors' conduct during inspection. It is the responsibility of the inspectors to develop attitudes and behaviours that enable them to focus on bringing about improvement for the sake of the children in our schools (MoES, 2010).

However, on responding on how reflective indicators are brought up during inspection routines during supervision, 26% of the participants had never heard or been asked questions regarding reflective indicators. This suggests that the promulgation of reflective indicators by supervisors and mentors remains at low levels. Thus, creating an understanding about the concept among teachers can enhance the application of the practice.

Concerning how both the mentor and the teacher are engaged in self-reflection, 32% of the respondents noted that they both engage by observing teacher reviews of the notes and drawing conclusions while 32% noted that they both engaged using the two approaches by engaging and observing teacher reviews of the notes and drawing conclusions as well as thinking about the lesson and formulating possible questions post-lessons. This suggests differences in approaches to engage in self-reflection or inconsistency in the mentoring programmes in school supervision. Barrera et al.(2009) points out that mentoring programmes are required to be examined periodically to assess the extent to which the needs of beginning teachers are satisfactorily met. However, looking into this matter critically could have a better result than when one approach is employed.

In conclusion, of the 100 respondents who participated in this study, 55% agreed that mentoring is an important part of teacher education that enhances reflective practice and the professional development of schools while 31% of them strongly agreed that mentoring is an important part of teacher education that enhances reflective practice and the professional development of schools. In line with this finding, Billet (2001) in Wilson and Demetriou (2007:214) emphasizes that Mentorship helps the mentee to identify with and imitate the mentor, receive reinforcement for positive behaviours and attitudes, learn how negative and inappropriate behaviours may interfere with emotional growth, and develop educational and work goals. Wherefore, teacher learning becomes the process of reflection and action through which teachers develop skills, and acquire knowledge and expertise.

While mentorship is an important part of teacher education and quality improvement, the different stakeholders need to take it seriously and all efforts should be put in place to ensure that mentoring is instituted in primary schools. This finding is justified by the $\chi^2=2.19$ and the significant (p) value of 0.032 at the standardized significant level of 0.05 in Table 4.14. Quality education in primary schools will improve 2.19 times when mentorship is taken as an important part of teacher education.

E. School Performance Reviews on the Improvement of Quality Primary Education in Uganda

The Inspectors in the Directorate of Education Standards and at local level through their work of inspection within districts, sub-counties and municipalities follow an inspection cycle to monitor the progress of conducting School Performance Reviews (SPR) in order to strengthen Reflective practice amongst staff (DES, 2012 & MoES, 2010). The ESA/DES Inspection tool goes a long way to complement the work of the school improvement planning in order to improve on the delivery of quality of education by enabling institutions to identify challenges and lay appropriate strategies to overcome such challenges.

Showing respondents' understanding regarding reflective Indicators based on multiple responses in Table 4.15, the respondents had various levels of understanding regarding reflective indicators. Of 181 respondents, 11% were not sure about what the term (reflective practice) means. This suggests the need to understand the term and be able to uphold Reflective

Indicators to self-evaluate teaching practices. Tucker, Stronge, and Gareis (2002) emphasize the significance of Reflection which provides an opportunity for teachers to self-evaluate their teaching and practices. Therefore, there is still a great deal to emphasize reflective indicators to avoid misunderstanding regarding the term and its specific indicators and lack of knowledge by the education stakeholders makes it difficult to obtain evidence on it and yet it forms an important part in self-evaluation. This is because individual schools administratively undertake self-evaluation without support of the district supervisors but by the school administrators. Then Inspection plays an important role in validating schools' self-evaluation, referring to national benchmarks based on the key components of the inspection approach that include a predetermined structure of Quality Indicators (QIs) such as the focus on evidence (MoES, 2010).

Showing Whether School Evaluation is very important in guiding the process of data collection on school and effectiveness of professional reflection of the primary teachers or not, 69% of the respondents agreed that School Evaluation is very important in guiding the process of data collection on school and effectiveness of professional reflection of primary teachers. This finding in Table 4.16 clearly portrays that school evaluation which is an element of School Performance Reviews is very instrumental in guiding the process of data collection on school and effectiveness of professional reflection of the primary teachers. Killeavy and Moloney (2010) highlighted the ability to reflect on practice as the basis for learning; and personal experiences are important in the teachers' development today, and reflection is one method that supports such development (Shoffner 2009); the ability to reflect evolves out of our experiences both as professionals and persons (Scanlan & Chernomas, 1997). Thus, various stakeholders need to uphold it in policy and practice.

Indicating the most common practices used by primary school teachers to reflect on their teaching based on 130 Multiple Responses, only 7% of the respondents stated all the above. The impression from these findings are presented in Table 4.17. There seem to be no standards and specific practices considered as a priority area for primary school teachers to reflect on their own teaching. For instance, the Primary teacher competence profile (2005) aims to achieve the same goal as the DES (2012) with more nuanced evaluative measures of quality education. The several competences required to improve the quality of education focus on competence 6: Skills of research and reflection. Under this competence, teachers are evaluated on the following areas: striving for continuous professional development, widening perception, Regular reflection on performance and Documentation and sharing reflection. However, this competence of skills of reflection seems to be ignored by the majority during support supervision. And yet they are key in the analysis on the supervision of teaching and professional improvement. Thus, policy makers need to come up with standardized specific guides and promulgate them among different stakeholders to enhance the quality of primary school education.

The findings in Table 4.18 clearly show that of the 100 respondents who participated in this study to determine the level of knowledge among different education stakeholders about the reflective practice, 59% clearly noted that they did not know what reflective practice was and had never heard of it. This finding suggests that knowledge of the concept of reflective practice as an element of School performance Reviews is still low among different education stakeholders. And yet inspectors develop attitudes and behaviours that help them to develop the kinds of relationships with teachers and leaders in schools and districts. They also enable them to be constructive and persuasive when providing feedback, while also remaining firm and focused above all on what is best for learners. It is through conducting School Performance Reviews (MoES, 2010) that reflective practice is strengthened. Therefore, an effort to popularize the concept needs to be made to improve its practice among various education stakeholders.

The results in Table 4.8 indicated that all the aspects examined under Supervisors' responsibilities are significantly associated with quality of education in primary schools. The results show that the quality education in primary schools will improve 5.12 times when issues of quality teaching are addressed such as reflective practice and internalized and implemented guidelines and policies, circulars issued by the Ministry of Education and Sports and as disseminated and explained by the District Education Office are prioritized. This finding is supported by the $x^2 = 5.12$ and the significant (p) value of 0.000 at the standardized significant level of 0.05. Seferođlu (2006) and Wilson and Demetriou (2007) argue that reflection on professional practice is one of the qualities that characterize a good teacher. It follows that one of the ways in which the prospective teacher can become a proficient teacher is through the development of values, knowledge and skills that support reflection on practice.

On whether ethos and indicators of reflective practice are enforced or not, the findings in Figure 4.8 show that 76% of the respondents disagreed that the ethos and indicators of reflective practice are not being enforced at schools. And yet there are Guidelines on Teacher Competences and Professionalism (2007) provided by the Directorate of Education Standards. This could suggest that some enforcement regarding the ethos and indicators of reflective practice is being done. However, the 24% of the respondents could be enforced in a very low, inconsistent and not in a specific manner. Thus, efforts need to be put in place by various stakeholders such that enforcement is consistently and widely done in all UPE schools so as to achieve desirable results on quality of education.

All in all, the findings of this study show that at the significant (p) value of 0.010 at the standardized significant level of 0.05 where the $x^2 = 3.08$, the quality of education will improve 3.08 times if the supervisors create opportunities to observe each other and facilitate experiences that develop teachers' capacity to reflect on their practice during support supervision and provide reliable feedback on the same.

CHAPTER SIX CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Summary

The study objectives were achieved and the methodology chosen for this study was appropriate for the tasks of this research because association between the independent and dependent variables was established using a questionnaire tool and a documentary review checklist tool. to obtain the needed data and analyse it to make conclusions and recommendations as spelt out below.

First, the effectiveness of support supervision towards the improvement of quality of primary school education in Uganda depends on the enabling environment and comprehensive system for UPE policy implementation for quality improvement in primary education. The education sector puts in place various departments that are decentralized for collaboration between departments under MoES to work effectively to improve the quality of education.

When effectiveness in support supervision was examined in areas that were independent of school inspectors, the relevance of methods/tools used in supervision; teachers' contribution during supervision; approaches of working out competence areas derived from self-assessment tools of teachers; quality teacher indicators and learning outcomes; and the importance of inspector's professional judgement, the minimum mean value of 1 and maximum mean value of 4 were used to help in the interpretation of data. In this regard, mean ranges from 3.26 to 4.00 portrayed that respondents strongly agreed with the items investigated on school supervision in primary schools indicated that school supervision practices in primary schools are very effective.

Additionally, the guides and strategic questions have also been set out to help the supervisors on how to offer support supervision during supervision of teaching (DES,2012). At the same time, 31% of the supervisors were from the school administration from UPE schools who had observed the guidelines to provide immediate support supervision for quality improvement irrespective of the challenges.

The challenge here is that there is a mix up of many guides provided in many documents such as the 'Competence Profile for primary teachers'(ESA,2005), 'How we inspect Part 6', 'How well are we led', 'How can we improve our school', among many others. There is need to have all items that measure the teacher's views or perceptions, experiences, self-evaluation etc under one document to help track the specific data on the professional reflection of the teacher and who is responsible for quality improvement in education development.

Additionally, the gaps in School inspection in the analysis of school inspection elements such as School Performance Reviews, Tools/methodology, Stakeholders' Responsibilities, and support supervision were identified.

Limitations in tool effectiveness, such as the self-assessment tool for primary teacher competence profile, have been identified as potential loopholes in ensuring quality education in primary schools. The unavailable data on teachers' self-assessments on shared experiences and documents could as well be as a result of use of outdated or inappropriate tools to obtain the evidenced data on teacher standards. In the guides on 'How we Inspect', it is clearly stated that, "Inspection is NOT just gathering data. Anybody can collect data, as long as he or she does it conscientiously and accurately. Data does not answer questions; it suggests questions which need to be asked". This makes this tool ineffective to collect professional responses if it allows anyone to supervise teaching profession of a teacher.

Also, the methodology used to enable the analysis of documented evidence on self-evaluation of teachers and implementation of quality improvement has not been systematically and effectively executed since data obtained on quality indicators focuses on pupil-teacher ratio and absenteeism of the teacher and learner outcomes. It is worth noting that supervision of learners is equally significant but tracking the details on the supervision of teachers' teaching outcome and evidenced data on self-evaluation is more significant towards the improvement of quality primary education.

And its no wonder that the research findings of De Grauwe (2001&2007), Diarra et al. (1997), Garforth (2004), Gumbi and Dlamini (1997), Lugaz et al. (2006), Solaux (1997) showed the lack of satisfaction among teachers and supervisors with the impact of supervision on the classroom in Africa.

If support supervision is to be effective, inspectors should use tools and methodologies which enable them to work consistently with high standards across the country. Aguti (2015) also commends school inspection capacity as a most vital component for teachers' productivity and teacher education as well as performance.

Secondly, this study determined the level of supervisors' role and responsibilities from the various departments under the Ministry of Education and Sports towards the improvement quality primary education in Uganda using mean values and standard deviations. Before examining the association between Stakeholders' responsibilities and quality of education, the minimum mean value was 1 and maximum mean value was 4 and these were used to help in the interpretation of data. And mean ranges from 3.26 to 4.00 which portrayed that the level of supervisors' responsibilities in primary schools is very high as summarized in Table 4.7 towards the improvement of quality primary education.

However, the quality improvements of primary education continue to suffer due to inconsistencies when it comes to the Inspectors' conduct of supervision which is not included in the methodology and yet they are required to be transparent, publicly available and share with school staff (MoES, 2010). What are supposed to be publicly available in regard to feedback on areas of strength and improvements are not availed to other stakeholders involved in taking significant decisions on quality improvements.

Also, stakeholders from various departments under MoES experience clashes on who is responsible for systematic supervision of teaching and teacher competence profiles support on the ground. For instance, DES developed the teacher competence profile as a tool for quality improvement of primary education but it was shelved and not put to use or supervised (DES, 2005). This remains as a challenge towards quality improvement of primary education. The study found out that the level of supervisor's responsibility was rated low because of less collaboration among the stakeholders when it comes to teacher empowerment during classroom supervision.

Thirdly, mentorship support was to a greater extent significant towards the improvement of quality primary education in Uganda according to the findings in Table 4.11 of this study, on the level of effectiveness among education stakeholders in providing a positive role model through demonstration of exemplary professional behaviours, no respondent rated themselves very ineffective and ineffective in providing a positive role model through demonstration of exemplary professional behaviours. Out of 100 participants, 55% rated themselves moderately effective in providing a positive role model through demonstration of exemplary professional behaviours.

Thus, mentorship support should be directly emphasized and legalized as mentorship policy with the intention to empower the teacher on how well he or she can engage in self-reflection and evaluation to become a reflective expert would have a significant association with improving the quality of education. Its through mentorship that skills and knowledge are passed on from one generation of teachers to another for a stable education system (Kram, 1985).

Lastly, the education sector has put out series on 'How we can improve quality education' where one of the documents on 'Evaluating and improving the quality of education' (DES, 2012) explains School Performance Review (SPR) as a form of supported self-evaluation carried out by a team from the school working with local inspectors, among others. SPR is considered as a good way of working out what you need to improve and the action you need to take.

Also, the 'Handbook on teacher education and training policies' (MoES, 2010) provides a policy reform on objective (i) To strengthen reflective practice amongst staff. SPR (MoES, 2010) is one of the strategies that enhances effective institutional and school planning through the support of school inspectors given to teachers and head teachers. And based on the implementations status in regard to SPR, the Directorate of Education Standards (DES) follows an inspection cycle where it monitors the progress of conducting of SPR.

None the less, the study found out that regarding how often are questions on reflective indicators were brought up during inspection routines, the results in Table 4.12 indicate that 9% of the 100 respondents who participated in this study indicated that they always ask questions on reflective indicators during inspection routines, while 45% were not sure of reflective practice. This implies that, to a less extent, School Performance Reviews as a strategy to strengthen reflective practice have not been done as they ought to be done to improve the quality of primary education.

B. Limitations

Collecting information on the elements of support supervision such as tools and methodology, School Performance Reviews, and Acts, guides, policies that speak about improving the quality of education was tedious. This required a lot of reading the documents since most of the participants' responses were specific due to the nature of the tool that was availed to them.

Due to the pandemic, the process of collecting data dragged on. This was because some of the participants who were both professional men and women from multiple sites were out of office and some had to take their time to fill in the questionnaire due to their busy schedules. They needed to be reminded via phone call which required a lot of patience.

The documents reviewed, especially the guides on improving the quality education, did not have consistent and specific quality indicators that would enable the implementation status of School Performance Reviews that strengthen reflective practice.

It was costly because it required money for transport to move to different offices, to print out the questionnaires and internet to collect data and store responses of the respondents on Google forms and Excel sheets; and printing out hard copies for those who had no time to fill in the online questionnaire.

The nature of data generated from the questionnaire required careful sorting, coding, cleaning and systematic documentation which was rigorous.

C. Recommendations

Efforts should be made to ensure the effectiveness of tools and methodologies used during support supervision, in order to analyze evidence and provide timely and constructive feedback to users, including teachers, researchers, and policy makers. This will promote effective support supervision and ultimately improve the quality of education.

There is need for standardized tools and methods with clear instructions on what is expected to adhere and promulgate evidenced data on reflective practices that enhance the quality of primary school education.

Stakeholders from various departments under the Ministry of Education and Sports should establish harmonious structures that speak to one another and that enhance the smooth running of the different departments.

Mentorship support has been indirectly mentioned as guidance provided to the teachers in the documents. It should be more loudly pronounced for clarity to enhance effective support supervision to get the desired teaching outcomes.

School Performance Reviews are very instrumental for strengthening professional reflection of the primary teachers (MoES, 2010). Thus various stakeholders should create awareness and educate teachers and other stakeholders on the significance of SPR to reduce on the mistakes through quality control mechanisms.

DES is mandated to ensure that inspections need and their professional conduct meet the highest standards (M0ES, 2010 & 2012) through School Performance Reviews (SPR).

Unfortunately, the results in this study indicated that the majority of the respondents (76%) disagreed that that ethos and indicators of reflective practice are enforced in schools. Therefore, efforts need to be made to ensure that ethos and indicators of reflective practice are enacted and consistently and widely enforced by the various stakeholders in all UPE schools so as to achieve desirable results.

Specific guides on the ethos and indicators for reflective practices during support supervision should be clearly stated and streamlined to guide the process for data collection and analysis so as to provide evidenced data to support the next course of action. If the standard indicators on reflective practice are well streamlined and assessed, they can support evidenced data for future research and guide the teacher policy process.

D. Suggestions for Further Research

Future Research should further investigate on the implementation status for School performance Reviews as a strategy to strengthen reflective practice for improvement.

The effectiveness of mentorship support guidelines to evaluate the teacher for improved performance.

Determine effective improvement plans that encourage stakeholder collaboration and measureable indicators to evaluate progress towards improvement goals

Determine tools and methods that support research evidence on a guide to evaluate school performance reviews that strengthen reflective practice.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1: QUESTIONNAIRE

Support Supervision and Quality Of primary school Education

Support supervision and Quality Education

Dear respondent,

I am Caroline Atuhairwe Kazooba a student of Masters in Research and Public Policy at Uganda Christian University. This study seeks for your voluntary responses and it will take only 10 minutes of your time. I kindly request you to respond to all questions . The information obtained is confidential and will be treated in aggregate. Thank you so much for supporting me on my academic program.

 carolinekazooba@gmail.com (not shared) [Switch account](#)

* Required

In which department of Ministry of Education and Sports / local government do you work for? *

Your answer

In your department/agency/ directorate what is your mandate, role and functions in fostering the implementation of UPE through reflective practice of different stakeholders? *

- Education officer
- Inspectors of schools
- Sub County chief
- Parish chief
- Regional Inspectors
- Chief Administrative Officer/Town Clerk
- Other
- Role/function:

What are considered reflective indicators within the evaluation tool as per the primary teacher competency profile? *

Your answer

As an inspector of schools, do you feel equipped or supported in understanding the reflective indicators? *

Yes

No

If no, how has this affected its implementation(reflective practice)? *

Your answer

Do you as a stakeholder feel adequately qualified to perform/ evaluate reflective practice? *

Yes

No

If yes, how is data collected on these indicators analyzed? *

Your answer

If no, how can this be addressed? *

Your answer

During inspection/evaluation and monitoring, does the observed stakeholder share impressions of the lesson and what it means for their personal teaching? *

Yes

No

If yes, how is this reported or analyzed? *

Your answer

What are the concerns about the quality of support supervision, inspection and monitoring of teachers specifically? *

Your answer

How often are questions on reflective indicators brought up during your inspection routines? Please select all that apply; *

- Always
- Once every inspection
- Questions about reflective indicators have been asked
- Don't know

What are the barriers/ problems observed during inspection or supervision on reflective practice? Please indicate; *

Your answer

What is the highest level of training in the formal education? *

- Certificate
- Diploma
- Degree
- Masters
- PhD
- Other

How many years of practice do you have in strengthening reflective teaching practices. Please select all that apply *

- 1-5 years
- 5-10 years
- 10-25 years +
- Don't know
- Other: _____

In your words, what is a reflective practice and why is it important in the teaching profession? *

Your answer _____

The supervisor and the supervisee both engage in self-reflection after classroom teaching observation. Please select: *

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

On a scale of 1 to 5 where 1 is the least effective and 5 is the most effective, how effectively do you use: A supervisory supportive checklist? *

1	2	3	4	5
☐				

On a scale of 1 to 5 where 1 is the least effective and 5 is the most effective, how effective do you provide a positive role model through demonstration of exemplary professional behaviors: Please select all that apply *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- Other: _____

What are the methods/tools commonly used to collect evidenced data on reflective practice? Please select all that apply *

- Reviewing records
- Perception measures and standards
- Listening to teachers and pupils
- Yes check list
- Don't know

In what ways do you think the indicators on reflective practice have contributed to the teaching profession? *

Your answer

The ethos and indicators of reflective practice are highly enforced. *

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Other: _____

What are the indicators of reflective practice? Please indicate; *

Your answer

On a scale of 1-5 with 5 being the highest, how much do you know about reflective practice? *

1 2 3 4 5

I have heard about reflective practice but don't know much about it

I know what reflective practice is and I try my best to model it

I know about reflective practice and can tell the observed teacher's capacity to reflect on teaching

I don't know what reflective practice is and never heard of it

what is the evidence of reflective practice in teaching? *

- Maintaining professional standards
- Documented record of work
- Shared personal reflection
- All the above
- Other
- Other: _____

What does support supervision mean? *

Your answer

Does Support supervision strengthen Professional reflection? *

- No
- Yes

If Yes/No, please indicate here below; *

Your answer

APPENDIX 2: DOCUMENTS REVIEW CHECKLIST

Documents	Why it's needed for the Study	Why it was reviewed
ESA Inspection Framework 2005/ Part 6: How we Inspect	It's an official document that provides primary data on how schools are Inspected. The document provides information on the responsibilities of DES and the methodology and tools application. The Agency produced guides to help education professionals improve the experiences and achievements of learners in schools. The document highlights that Improvements in learners' experiences will only be achieved if all the key players work closely together on these shared goals	It entails a structure on how improvement activities should be implemented and other significant information that feeds into the study objectives
UPE for You and Uganda Handbook on TIET and Training policies	It provides key policy messages and stakeholders' responsibilities To be informed of the various teacher reforms and their implementation status	Reviewed Reviewed
Journal: Transforming School Supervision into a Tool for Quality Improvement (2007)	It explains the effectiveness of supervision service as a key tool to monitor and improve education quality. https://www.jstor.org/stable/27715425	Reviewed
Part 3: How well are our learners doing?(2012)		Reviewed
Part 1: How can we improve our school?	To appreciate the different activities done by the stakeholders in improving quality of primary education	Reviewed
Budgeting and Implementation Guidelines for Primary and Secondary Schools 2019	To understand the guidelines for primary and the process involved in informing policy actions for implementation	Reviewed
Education Service Notice,2012	To identify the specific a set of teacher standards evaluated to inform policy actions and implementation	Reviewed
KCCA Education Q3 performance	To identify the number of Government aided primary schools and be able to determine the sample size	Reviewed
Improving the quality of teacher education in sub-Saharan Africa (2018)	It provides statistics on learning outcomes and the need for quality teachers	Reviewed
Teaching policies and learning outcomes in Sub-Saharan Africa (2016)	It states the launched Continental Education Strategy for Africa (CESA 2016-2025) ¹ which envisages a new generation of African citizens who are effective change agents for the continent's sustainable development. And talks about the Teachers situated at the heart of this strategy as part of "qualitative systems of education and training [that] provide the African continent with efficient human resources adapted to African core values."	Reviewed
The Education in Uganda	To be informed about the history of our national education and track the progress of its developments in line with policy implementation	Reviewed
The Government White Paper 1992 on Education	To appreciate its authority and the fundamental ideologies on the teacher as the backbone of education improvements	Reviewed
Competence profile (2005)	It's a professional tool that guides teachers and all other stakeholders in primary education on identifying the desired competences of the primary school teacher in Uganda. The profile helps the stakeholders to direct their efforts appropriately in their quest for teacher improvement.	Reviewed
Policies and Guidelines Annex 5	The document provides guidelines on Policy, Planning, Roles & Responsibilities of Stakeholders in the Implementation of Universal Primary Education (UPE) for Districts and Urban Council (2008)	Reviewed

APPENDIX 3: CONSENT LETTER FROM UCU-REC

10th September, 2021

To whom It may Concern

Dear Sir/Madam,

RE: INTRODUCTORY LETTER FOR KAZOوبا CAROLINE

Warm greetings from Uganda Christian University!

This serves to introduce the above named; **Kazooba Caroline**, as our student pursuing a Masters degree of Research and Public Policy registered number **S19/M07/008**.

Caroline is conducting a research as a requirement for the award of the above mentioned degree entitled; *Support supervision analysis and implementation of Quality Education in Public Schools in Uganda. A Case of Education Standards Agency*.

She has fulfilled all clearance requirements such as getting Research Ethics Approval from UCUREC which is accredited and regulated by Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST).

Any assistance given to her to achieving this goal will be highly welcome.

Thank you so much.

Yours faithfully,

Prof. Peter Ubomba-Jaswa
Head, Research, Grants & Publications
Uganda Christian University
pubombajaswa.ucu.ac.ug

cc. Executive Secretary, UNCST

A Complete Education for A Complete Person

P.O. Box 4, Mukono, Uganda (East Africa), Plot 67-173, Bishop Tucker Road, Mukono Hill,
Tel: +256 (0) 31 235 0800, Web: www.ucu.ac.ug UgandaChristianUniversity @UCUniversity
Founded by the Province of the Church of Uganda. Chartered by the Government of Uganda

APPENDIX 4: CONSENT LETTER FROM DIRECTORATE EDUCATION KCCA

MEMORANDUM

REF : DES/KCCA/508
DATE : 5TH OCTOBER, 2021
TO : SUPERVISORS EDUCATION SERVICES
COPY : TOWN CLERKS
FROM : DIRECTOR EDUCATION AND SOCIAL SERVICES
SUBJECT : INTRODUCTORY LETTER FOR KAZOوبا CAROLINE

The Head, Research, Grants and Publications at Uganda Christian University in a letter dated 10th September, 2021 introduced the above mentioned student who is pursuing a Masters degree of research and public policy.

Caroline intends to conduct research on the topic titled; *Support supervision analysis and implementation of Quality education in Public Schools in Uganda. A case of Education Standards Agency.*

The purpose of this communication, is to request you to accord her the necessary assistance to undertake this research.

Herewith attached is the letter from Uganda Christian University.

For a better City

Namuddu Juliet Nambi

APPENDIX 5: CONSENT LETTER FROM MINISTRY OF EDUCATION AND SPORTS

Telegram: "EDUCATION"
Telephone: 234451/8
Fax: 234920

Ministry of Education and Sports
Embassy House
P.O. Box 7063
Kampala, Uganda
Website: www.education.go.ug
E-mail: abdulmalik.educ@gmail.com

In any correspondence on

this subject please quote: ADM/48/315/01

27th January 2022

Dear participant,

To whom it may concern

This serves to introduce to you Caroline Atuhairwe Kazooba a student at Uganda Christian University who is in pursuit of Masters of Research and Public Policy. Her study is focused on: "*Support Supervision analysis and implementation of Quality Primary Education Uganda*". This research study is one of the requirements for the award of Masters of Research and Public Policy of Uganda Christian University. Uganda Christian University Research Ethics, which is accredited and regulated by Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (**UNCST**) approved her topic of study. The university wrote a letter of introduction to key stakeholders, Basic Education Department being key in the implementation of Universal Primary Education (UPE), assigned Abdul Malik Muwanga to take lead in collaborating and making sure that the study is successfully concluded.

It is against this background that you have been selected to participate in this research. Find herein the attached link and answer all the questions to the best of your knowledge. <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSemRQiQ0r67IRgCjCq7pniVfKk2Nht--3yVkuYFJ087bONSeQ/viewform?vc=0&c=0&w=1&flr=0>

Thank you for your kind and timely responses and many blessings.

Abdul Malik Muwanga
Senior Education Officer pre-primary

Caroline A. Kazooba
Student

APPENDIX 6: CERTIFICATE OF PROOF THAT DISSERTATION HAS BEEN EDITED

MUKOTANI RUGYENDO

P.O. BOX 31178

KAMPALA

TEL: 0701707093

/0777752574

1 May 2022

CERTIFICATE OF PROOF THAT DISSERTATION HAS BEEN EDITED

This is to certify that the Master’s degree dissertation titled, **Support Supervision Analysis and Implementation of Quality Primary Education in Uganda by Kazooba Atuhairwe Caroline**, has been reviewed and corrected in order to ensure clarity of expression and consistency regarding key style aspects like general grammar, sentence structure to achieve logical flow and effectiveness of meaning, all-round punctuation, and specific aspects including: long-windedness, wordiness and repetition; subject-verb agreement; use of articles; US English spellings; citation and referencing.

Mukotani Rugyendo

Professional Editor